

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D7.7 Report on legal and ethics monitoring

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
CV2X	Cellular Vehicle to Everything
CA	Consortium Agreement
D2D	Device to Device
DG-CNECT PO	Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology Project Officer
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
EAB	External Advisory Board
EP	Ethics Panel
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi Access Mobile Edge Computing
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
NDPR	National Data Protection Regulation(s)
OAI	Open Air Interface
RAN	Radio Access Network
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle to Network
V2P	Vehicle to Pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This document constitutes Deliverable D7.7. The deliverable is titled “D7.7: Report on legal and ethics monitoring v1.0: Initial report”. It is the result of the work conducted in WP7, Task 7.4 “Legal framework, ethics & gender balance”.

This document provides the reader with an initial report on 5G-ROUTES project activities related to legal, ethics, and gender concerns. This initial report (D7.7) defines legal, ethics, and gender guidelines to guide and drive the 5G-ROUTES partners when executing their project activities.

The main purpose of this initial report is to create awareness about ethics, legal, and gender issues, as well as to create a mindset among all consortium members to avoid potential risks related to such issues. To do so, this report presents a set of common methods and procedures for the project research process, which should be applied by all consortium members.

The guidelines and recommendations that constitutes the basis for the Research Ethics Protocol are defined according to and in order to ensure compliance with the current legal and ethics framework. In this respect, 5G-ROUTES Consortium partners commit to adhere to fundamental ethical principles and relevant national, Union and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/c 364/01), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679), the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, and the European Convention on Human Rights. In relation to the ethics issues, the respective ethics protocols included in this report materialise this commitment by identifying the partner’s responsibilities and describing the procedures and methodology to ensure that 5G-ROUTES research activities, test beds and field trial use cases are ethically sound.

Throughout the project, the 5G-ROUTES partners will adhere to the Research Ethics Protocol in their work and its implementation will be monitored and refined including an update on the review procedures: the second version of this document (D7.8 “Report on legal and ethics monitoring final version”) will be delivered at month 35 just before the end of project on month 36.

Compliance of the 5G-ROUTES project research activities and field tests, with legislation, ethics standards and guidelines will be also reinforced and assured with the establishment of the Ethics Panel of experts.

2 Introduction and scope

This document constitutes Deliverable D7.7. The deliverable is titled “D7.7: Report on legal and ethics monitoring v1.0: Initial report”. It is the result of the work conducted in WP7, Task T7.4 “Legal framework, ethics & gender balance”.

This initial report was prepared by considering the initial assessment of potential legal, ethics, and gender concerns relating to the project’s activities as known at this early stage of the project (project month 3) by also considering the Description of Action (DoA) and the (ongoing) project’s research activities that will deliver the following reports:

1. D1.1 “Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0”;
2. D1.7 “Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0 Interim (v1.0) of reports”
3. Description of Action (DoA – Part A and Part B)

The information, available at this stage, about the project’s external participations and the planned cases/scenarios, and validation methods gives an initial picture of:

1. In case of involvement of human beings, how and when research will involve them;
2. Initial potential legal and ethics concerns on individuals’ recruitment;
3. Processing and Protection of personal data EU and national data protection law, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR);
4. Processing and Protection of project other data (Research Information and Business/ Trade Secrets);
5. Gender perspectives.

The purpose of D7.7 is to identify and describe the procedures and methodology to ensure that 5G-ROUTES research activities and field trial (use cases) are both legally and ethically sound, provide due consideration to gender balance issues, and that data from research participants is stored according to EU and national regulations to ensure their privacy.

In this context, it aims to fulfil the following main objectives:

- Provide guidelines to ensure adherence of the project’s partners with ethics requirements imposed by the Grant Agreement, specifically:
 - D8.1 “H - Requirement No. 1” (due month 6);
 - D8.2 “POPD - Requirement No. 2” (due month 6).
- Provide recommendations to ensure that the processing of personal data for research purposes by the project’s partners comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and its national implementation laws.
- Provide an information sheet and an informed consent form template to the project’s partners for the purpose of communicating about the project with third parties and involve third parties in events.
- Provide a baseline document for the Academic Ethics Committee of TTU to review and approve the ethics requirements of the project. The latter will monitor all ethics-related aspects in 5G-ROUTES project and will be consulted by the project consortium on potential ethics impacts of the activities undertaken during the project’s lifecycle.
- Provide recommendations on how to make due considerations in terms of gender balance in relation to the project’s management and participation as well as in the proposed research methodologies.
- Provide recommendations for the establishment of an Ethics Panel (EP) of experts consisting of experts on ethics, privacy, gender and legal issues. The EP will monitor all legislative, gender balance and ethics-related aspects in the 5G-ROUTES project and will consult the project consortium on the respective potential impacts of the activities undertaken during the project’s lifecycle.

The following sections present the mapping of the projects' output with the various parts of this document and give an overview of the document and its structure.

2.1 Mapping Projects' Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed in Task T7.4 and the documentation of the results thereof in this deliverable.

Table 1. Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions for Task T7.4 / Deliverable D7.7

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.7: Report on legal and ethics monitoring v1.0: Initial report			
TASKS			
T7.4 "Legal framework, ethics & gender balance"	Manage the ethical issues concerning the design of the information and consent forms that will be used in case of involvement of human beings in the field trials.	Chapter 4	5G-ROUTES Research Ethics Protocol builds upon a legal and ethics background framework, including EU definitions of research ethics on human beings' involvement, detailed description of international ethics standards, legislations and codes of conduct. This aims to ensure the compliance of project activities from the legal and ethics perspectives.
	Investigate, design and monitor all the procedures and protocols for handling legal issues during the project's lifetime.	Chapter 5	Initial analysis of research activities is performed by reviewing testbeds/test site, use cases/, External Advisory Board and Ethics Panel described in DoA, and by integrating further details coming from initial inputs of the project activities (i.e. use cases and test validations). This aims to identify potential ethics concerns with respect to relative background framework.
	Delivery of the ethical and legal guidelines early in the project to drive the partners in their activities. Produce the research ethical protocol as part of	Chapter 6	Initial definition of the Research Ethics Protocol, consisting on guidelines and recommendations on how to handle the potential project ethics and legal concerns.

	deliverable D7.4 for the project, stipulating the ethical principles that the 5G-ROUTES partners will adhere to in their work.		
	Gender balance will also be monitored during the course of the project to ensure that the female/male ratio is maintained as close to 1:1 as possible for people employed during its course.	Chapter 4, sub-section 4.3	5G-ROUTES' approach to gender balance follows the guidance on gender equality in Horizon 2020 as recommended by the European Commission.
Support bodies to the governance structure: Ethics Panel	Chaired by the Legal & Ethics Leader (Mr. Henri Schasmin (TTU)) and includes legal advisors of the participating members (experts on ethics, privacy, gender and legal issues).	Chapter 5, Section 5.2.1.2	The role of the Ethics Panel is to monitor the objectives and implications of the project's research, to ensure that it conforms to the highest ethical standards.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Following the introduction, the report structure is as follows:

1. Chapter 3 "Research Legal Background" presents the EU research legal background, the specificities of the countries where trials will be conducted (Finland, Estonia, Latvia), and the main legal concerns.
2. Chapter 4 "Research Ethics Background" describes the EU research ethics background, national ethics background, gender perspective, privacy, and the main ethics concerns.
3. Chapter 5 "5G-ROUTES Research Process Overview" summarizes the project purpose, research process, advisory boards/Ethics Panel, testbeds/test site, use cases, and trials.
4. Chapter 6 "5G-ROUTES Research Ethics Policy and Protocols" describes the 5G-ROUTES ethics safeguard measures, recruitment rules, recruitment criteria, recruitment procedures, privacy and personal data protection, the EU Framework on data protection, the 5G-ROUTES privacy and data protection rules, and the project data confidentiality issue.
5. Chapter 7 presents the conclusions and next actions.
6. References and annexes close the report:
 1. Annex I provides an overview of the human participation related activities in 5G-ROUTES;
 2. Annex II provides the health and safety regulations in 5G-ROUTES;
 3. Annex III provides an Ethics checklist for Ethics responsible partners at each pilot to ensure that all necessary steps are taken to abide with the 5G-ROUTES Ethics policy;
 4. Annex IV presents the Ethics Controlling Report template including Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) to be circulated to relevant partners and the results will be presented in D3.5;
 5. Annex V gives the information sheet example template;
 6. Annex VI gives the informed consent template;

7. Annex VII gives the anonymous informed consent template;
8. Annex VIII gives the non-anonymous informed consent template; and
9. Annex IX gives the NDA template for EAB.

Figure 1 depicts the flow followed in Task T7.4, resulting in the definition of the Research Ethics Protocol and procedures put in place for the whole duration of the project.

Figure 1. Illustration of the flow followed in Task T7.4, resulting in the definition of the Research Ethics Protocol

3 Research Legal Background

3.1 EU Research Legal Background

Main Regulation of Research and Development (Horizon 2020). REGULATION (EU) No 1291/2013 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 11 December 2013 **Establishing Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)** [1].

General information. This Regulation establishes Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) ("Horizon 2020") and determines the framework governing Union support to research and innovation activities, thereby strengthening the European scientific and technological base and fostering benefits for society as well as better exploitation of the economic and industrial potential of policies of innovation, research and technological development.

General and specific objectives. According to Article 5 General objective, priorities and specific objectives – The general objective of Horizon 2020 is to contribute to building a society and an economy based on knowledge and innovation across the Union by leveraging additional research, development and innovation funding and by contributing to attaining research and development targets, including the target of 3 % of GDP for research and development across the Union by 2020. It shall thereby support the implementation of the Europe 2020 strategy and other Union policies, as well as the achievement and functioning of the European Research Area (ERA).

Implementation. According to Article 15 Evolving nature of science, technology, innovation, economies and society – Horizon 2020 shall be implemented in a manner ensuring that the priorities and actions supported are relevant to changing needs and take account of the evolving nature of science, technology, innovation, economies and society in a globalised world, where innovation includes business, organisational, technological, societal and environmental aspects.

Gender equality. According to Article 16 Gender equality – Horizon 2020 shall ensure the effective promotion of gender equality and the gender dimension in research and innovation content. Particular attention shall be paid to ensuring gender balance, subject to the situation in the field of research and innovation concerned, in evaluation panels and in bodies such as advisory groups and expert groups. The gender dimension shall be adequately integrated in research and innovation content in strategies, programmes and projects and followed through at all stages of the research cycle.

Ethical principles. According to Article 19 Ethical principles – All the research and innovation activities carried out under Horizon 2020 shall comply with ethical principles and relevant national, Union and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols.

Particular attention shall be paid to the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination and the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

Research and innovation activities carried out under Horizon 2020 shall have an exclusive focus on civil applications.

Public-private partnerships. According to Article 25 Public-private partnerships – Horizon 2020 may be implemented through public-private partnerships where all the partners concerned commit to supporting the development and implementation of pre-competitive research and of innovation activities of strategic importance to the Union's competitiveness and industrial leadership or to addressing specific societal challenges.

Main Regulation of Electronic Communications. Directive 2002/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 March 2002 on a common regulatory framework for electronic communications networks and services (Framework Directive) [2].

The Framework Directive establishes a harmonised framework for the regulation of electronic communications services, electronic communications networks, associated facilities and associated services. It lays down tasks of national regulatory authorities and establishes a set of procedures to ensure the harmonised application of the regulatory framework throughout the Community.

The Framework Directive as well as the Specific Directives are without prejudice to obligations imposed by national law in accordance with Community law or by Community law in respect of services provided using electronic communications networks and services.

The Framework Directive as well as the Specific Directives are without prejudice to measures taken at Community or national level, in compliance with Community law, to pursue general interest objectives, in particular relating to content regulation and audio-visual policy.

The following sections present the EU research legal background and the specificities of the countries where trials will be conducted (Finland, Estonia, Latvia) and of which project partners should be aware of.

3.2 Finnish Research Legal Background

Main Regulation of Research and Development. In Finland, research and development activities are regulated by **Government Decree on the Research and Innovation Council of Finland** [3]. For addressing important matters relating to the targeting, follow-up, evaluation and coordination of research, technology and innovation policy there shall be a Research and Innovation Council of Finland. The Council shall assist the Government and its ministries in matters within the purview of the Council.

The remit of the Council shall be to:

1. follow national and international developments in research, technology and innovation;
2. evaluate the state and developments within the sphere of its authority;
3. address major matters relating to the development of science, technology and innovation policy and the human resources they entail and prepare proposals and plans concerning these for the Government;
4. address matters relating to the development and allocation of public research and innovation funding on a preparatory basis for the Government;
5. coordinate Government activities in the field of science, technology and innovation policy.

Main Regulation of Electronic Communications. In Finland, communications development activities are regulated by Act on Electronic Services and Communication in the Public Sector [4].

The objective of the Act on Electronic Services and Communication in the Public Sector is to improve smoothness and rapidity of services and communication as well as information security in the administration, in the courts and other judicial organs and in the enforcement authorities by promoting the use of electronic data transmission.

The Act contains provisions on the rights, duties and responsibilities of the authorities and their customers in the context of electronic services and communication.

3.3 Estonian Research Legal Background

Main Regulation of Research and Development. In Estonia, research and development activities are regulated by the Organisation of Research and Development Act [5].

The purpose of the Organisation of Research and Development Act is to provide the grounds for the organisation of research and development and to ensure legal means for the preservation and further development of scientific and technological creation as a component of Estonian culture and the Estonian economy.

Main Regulation of Electronic Communications. In Estonia, communications development activities are regulated by the Electronic Communications Act [6].

The purpose of Electronic Communications Act is to create the necessary conditions for the development of electronic communications to promote the development of electronic communications networks and electronic communications services without giving preference to specific technologies and to ensure the protection of the interests of users of electronic communications services by promoting free competition and the purposeful and just planning, allocation and use of radio frequencies and numbering.

Electronic Communications Act provides requirements for the public electronic communications networks and publicly available electronic communications services, for the use of electronic contact details for direct marketing, for the conduct of radiocommunication, for the management of radio frequencies and numbering and for radio equipment as well as state supervision over the compliance with these requirements and liability for the violation of these requirements.

3.4 Latvian Research Legal Background

Main Regulation of Research and Development. In Latvia, research and development activities are regulated by Law on Scientific Activity [7]. The purpose of Law on Scientific Activity is to strengthen the role of the State in the fostering of science as a particularly important factor in the development of society.

The Law on Scientific Activity prescribes the unity of science and higher education, the rights, liabilities, independence, and academic freedom of scientists, professional and social security, and the competence and obligations of State authorities in the ensuring of scientific activity.

According to Law on Scientific Activity Section 3. Right to Perform Scientific Activity – Any person, regardless of race, ethnicity, gender, language, age, political or religious conviction, social origin, or material, family or employment situation, and other circumstances, has the right to perform scientific activity.

According to Law on Scientific Activity Section 9. Transparency of Information regarding Scientific Research - information regarding scientific research financed from the State or local government budget shall be transparent. An institution responsible for the performance of scientific research financed from the State budget or the budget of derived public persons, which has commissioned the research, shall ensure general access to research results. Access to information that is related to scientific research may be restricted in the cases specified by Law.

According to Law on Scientific Activity Section 13. Ensuring of Scientific Activity – The Ministry of Education and Science shall:

1. develop the State policy for the development of science and technology;
2. prepare a request for the allocation of annual State budget resources for the ensuring of scientific activity according to the State policy for the development of science and technology;
3. may enter into delegation and participation agreements regarding the introduction of international cooperation projects and programmes, ensuring the recognition of Latvian science and the shaping of public understanding regarding the importance of science for the development of a sustainable state;

4. co-ordinate international cooperation programmes in the fields of research and technology and in accordance with the procedures stipulated by the Cabinet, ensure support for participation in such programmes;
5. maintain and update the National Research Information System.

The Cabinet shall:

1. determine the State policy for the development of science and technology, as well as innovation;
2. approve the priority scientific fields and State research programmes;
3. determine the fields and subfields of science of Latvia;
4. perform other activities specified in Law on Scientific Activity.

The Ministry of Economics shall:

1. develop innovation policy;
2. may enter into delegation and participation agreements regarding the introduction and implementation of international technology transfer projects and programmes, popularisation of examples of innovation good practices and the implementation of innovation active public awareness measures.

According to Law on Scientific Activity Section 14. Latvian Council of Science – The Latvian Council of Science shall implement the State policy for science and technological development by fulfilling the following functions:

1. strategic implementation of science policy and strategic communication of science;
2. planning and implementation of scientific research programmes;
3. ensuring of scientific expert-examination for the needs of public and private sector;
4. promotion and coordination of international scientific cooperation.

According to Law on Scientific Activity Section 34. Financing of Fundamental and Applied Research –

1. Financing of fundamental and applied research shall be allocated to specific projects in the form of grants in accordance with competition procedures. Project applications shall be submitted by scientists. The topics, purposes, and tasks of the research shall be formulated by the scientists themselves.
2. The main criterion for the allocation of a grant shall be the scientific merit of a project.
3. The Latvian Council of Science shall evaluate, administer fundamental and applied research projects, and distribute financing in accordance with the procedures laid down by the Cabinet. Each year the Latvian Council of Science shall submit to the Ministry of Education and Science a report on the use of the State budget funds allocated to the fundamental and applied research.
4. The Cabinet shall approve the priorities of scientific fields for the financing of fundamental and applied research once every four years according to the State policy for the development of science and technology.

According to Law on Scientific Activity Section 36. Financing of Market-oriented Research – The financing of market-oriented research shall take place by allocating State budget resources to projects of a practical nature the purpose of which is to promote the integration of science and manufacturing, the development of technology-oriented fields, and the creation of new jobs. The Ministry of Education and Science shall distribute financing for market-oriented research projects on the basis of a scientific and economic expert-examination and in accordance with Cabinet regulations. Experts of the Latvian Council of Science shall perform the scientific expert-examination of the projects.

Main Regulation of Electronic Communications. In Latvia, communications development activities are regulated by Electronic Communications Law [8].

The purpose of Electronic Communications Law is:

1. promote the provision of electronic communications networks and the development of electronic communications services;

2. promote the development of competition in the provision of electronic communications networks and the provision of electronic communications services;
3. promote the implementation of a simplified and transparent electronic communications merchant registration regime;
4. ensure the regulation of electronic communications networks and electronic communications services independent of electronic communications technology;
5. ensure the rational and effective use of scarce resources in the electronic communications sector;
6. ensure the protection of the interests of the State, users and electronic communications merchants;
7. promote the accessibility of the universal service;
8. ensure the integrity and interconnectivity of electronic communications networks, and continuity of electronic communications services;
9. ensure the protection of user data, including personal data.

The Electronic Communications Law determines the competence, rights, and obligations of users, electronic communications merchants, private electronic communications network owners and State administrative institutions which are associated with the regulation of the electronic communications sector, the provision of electronic communications networks and the provision of electronic communications services, as well as the use and administration of scarce resources.

This Electronic Communications Law shall not apply to the provision of information society services and the information content thereof, which are transmitted or received in electronic communications networks.

3.5 Legal aspects of Privacy, including General Data Protection Regulation and National Data Protection Regulations

3.5.1 General Data Protection Regulation

1. General information. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a European Union privacy regulation that takes effect on 25th May, 2018.

The GDPR is designed to give individuals control over their personal data and is an important effort for protecting individual rights and freedoms.

The GDPR applies to any organisations based in the EU and organisations, wherever they are located, that are selling goods and services in the European Union or processing the personal data of individuals in the European Union.

According to General Data Protection Regulation the protection of natural persons in relation to the processing of personal data is a fundamental right.

Article 8(1) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and Article 16(1) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union provide that everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.

The principles of, and rules on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of their personal data should, whatever their nationality or residence, respect their fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular their right to the protection of personal data.

The processing of personal data should be designed to serve mankind. The right to the protection of personal data is not an absolute right; it must be considered in relation to its function in society and be balanced against other fundamental rights, in accordance with the principle of proportionality.

In terms of the 5G-ROUTES project and General Data Protection Regulation principles, it is important to emphasize, that the economic and social integration resulting from the functioning of the internal market has led to a substantial increase in cross-border flows of personal data.

2. Main Principles of Data Processing and Protection. With respect to **data processing, protection and privacy**, the 5G-ROUTES project must be implemented in a way that safeguards the fundamental rights for natural persons. As stated in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), this implies compliance with the principles of:

1. **lawfulness, fairness and transparency;**
2. **purpose limitation;**
3. **data minimisation;**
4. **accuracy;**
5. **storage limitation;**
6. **integrity and confidentiality;**
7. **accountability.**

Data Protection Impact Assessment. According to *GDPR Article 35 Data protection impact assessment*, the project team shall, in certain cases, prior to the processing, carry out an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data.

Data protection impact assessment is required, if using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

A data protection impact assessment shall in particular be required in the case of:

1. a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling, and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person;
2. processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10; or
3. a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale.

The project team shall seek the advice of the data protection officer, when carrying out a data protection impact assessment.

The data protection impact assessment contains at least:

1. a systematic description of the envisaged processing operations and the purposes of the processing, including, where applicable, the legitimate interest pursued by the project team;
2. an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to the purposes;
3. an assessment of the risks to the rights and freedoms of data subjects referred to in point 1;
4. the measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data and to demonstrate compliance with this regulation taking into account the rights and legitimate interests of data subjects and other persons concerned.

Data Protection Officer. According to *GDPR Article 37 Data protection officer*, the controller and the processor designate a data protection officer in any case where:

1. the processing is carried out by a public authority or body;

2. the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing operations which, by virtue of their nature, their scope and/or their purposes, require regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale.

3.5.2 Data Protection Regulation in Finland

1. Data Protection Act [9]. This Data Protection Act specifies and supplements Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), hereafter the Data Protection Regulation, and its national application.

This Act applies within the scope of application of Article 2 of the Data Protection Regulation. This Act and the Data Protection Regulation also apply, with the exception of Article 56 and Chapter VII of the Regulation, to the processing of personal data in the course of activities referred to in points (a) and (b) of Article 2(2), unless otherwise provided elsewhere by law.

Finnish law applies to the processing of personal data in the context of activities of an establishment of a controller or a processor located in the territory of the European Union, if the controller is established in Finland. If the law of a foreign state applies to the processing of personal data and derogations are made by virtue of it in accordance with Article 89(2) of the Data Protection Regulation from the rights provided for the protection of the data subject, the safeguards laid down for the protection of the data subject in section 31 below shall, however, be complied with irrespective of the choice of applicable law.

2. Data Processing for Scientific Purposes. According to *Data Protection Act Chapter 2 Legal basis for processing in certain cases, Section 4 Lawfulness of Processing, P 3 and 4* – Personal data may be processed in accordance with point (e) of Article 6(1) of the Data Protection Regulation if:

1. the processing is necessary for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes and it is proportionate to the aim of public interest pursued; or
2. the processing of research material and cultural heritage material containing personal data and the processing of personal data included in their metadata for archiving purposes is necessary and proportionate to the aim of public interest pursued and to the rights of the data subject.

According to *Data Protection Act Section 29 Processing of personal identity codes* – A personal identity code may be processed if the data subject has given consent to it or if so provided by law. A personal identity code may also be processed if it is necessary to uniquely identify the data subject for scientific research purposes.

According to *Data Protection Act Section 31 According to Data Protection Act Section 31 Derogations and safeguards relating to processing of personal data for scientific and historical research purposes and statistical purposes* - Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes, the rights of the data subject laid down in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 of the Data Protection Regulation may be derogated from, where necessary, provided that:

1. the processing is based on an appropriate research plan;
2. a person or group responsible for the research has been designated; and
3. the personal data are used and disclosed only for scientific or historical research purposes or for other compatible purposes, and the procedure followed is also otherwise such that data concerning a given individual are not revealed to outsiders.

3. Supervisory Authority. According to *Data Protection Act Section 8 Data Protection Ombudsman* -

In Finland, the national supervisory authority referred to in the Data Protection Regulation is **the Data Protection Ombudsman**, who works under the auspices of the Ministry of Justice. The Data Protection Ombudsman is autonomous and independent in his or her activities.

4. Data subject's right to address Supervisory Authority. Where a natural person has reported a suspected infringement of the provisions subject to the supervision of the Data Protection Ombudsman to the Ombudsman, the identity of the reporting person shall be kept secret, if it is estimated, based on the circumstances, that revealing the identity would cause detriment to the reporting person.

5. Data Protection Officer. No additional requirements are set out. Activities according to General Data Protection Regulation.

3.5.3 Data Protection Regulation in Estonia

1. Personal Data Protection Act ([10]). Personal Data Protection Act regulates:

(1) protection of natural persons upon processing of personal data to the extent in which it elaborates and supplements the provisions contained in Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (OJ L 119, 04.05.2016, pp. 1-88);

(2) protection of natural persons upon processing of personal data by law enforcement authorities in the prevention, detection and proceedings of offences and execution of punishments.

This Data Protection Act provides for:

1. standards for implementation of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council;
2. standards for transposition of Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA (OJ L 119, 04.05.2016, pp. 89-131);

(3) procedure for exercise of state supervision over compliance with the requirements for the processing of personal data;

(4) liability for the violation of the requirements for processing of personal data.

2. Data Processing for Scientific Purposes. According to *Data Protection Act Chapter 2 Specific Grounds for Processing of Personal Data, § 6. Processing of personal data for needs of scientific and historical research and official statistics* -

(1) Personal data may be processed without the consent of the data subject for the needs of scientific research and official statistic, in particular in a pseudonymised format or a format which provides equivalent level of protection. Prior to transmission of personal data for processing for the needs of scientific research or official statistics, personal data shall be replaced by pseudonymised data or data in a format which provides equivalent level of data protection.

(2) Depseudonymisation or any other method by which the data not enabling identification of persons are changed again into the data which enable identification of persons are only permitted for the needs of additional scientific research or official statistics. Processors of personal data shall designate a person identified by name who has access to the information allowing pseudonymisation.

(3) Processing of data concerning any data subjects for the needs of scientific research or official statistics without the consent of the data subject in a format which enables identification of the data subject is permitted only in the case the following conditions are met:

1. the purposes of data processing can no longer be achieved after removal of the data enabling identification or it would be unreasonably difficult to achieve these purposes;
2. there is overriding public interest for it in the estimation of the persons conducting scientific research or compiling official statistics;
3. the scope of obligations of the data subject is not changed based on the processed personal data or the rights of the data subject are not excessively damaged in any other manner.

(4) If scientific research is based on special categories of personal data, the ethics committee of the area concerned shall first verify compliance with the terms and conditions provided for in this section. If there is no ethics committee in the scientific area, the compliance with the requirements shall be verified by the Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate. With regard to any personal data retained at the National Archives, the National Archives shall have the rights of the ethics committee.

(5) For the purposes of this Act, scientific research is deemed to also include any analyses and studies by executive power which are carried out for the purposes of policy development. In order to prepare these, the executive power has the rights to make queries to databases of another controller or processor and process the personal data received. The Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate shall verify, prior to the beginning of the specified processing of personal data, compliance with the terms and conditions provided for in this section, except in the case the objectives of the studies conducted for policy development and the scope of processing of personal data derive from legislation.

(6) Where personal data are processed for the purpose of scientific research or official statistics, the controller or processor may restrict the rights of data subjects provided for in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council insofar as the exercise of these rights is likely to make the achievement of the objectives of the scientific research or official statistics impossible or impedes it to a significant extent.

3. Supervisory Authority. According to *Data Protection Act Chapter 5 State and Administrative Supervision, Supervisory Authority, § 51 Formation of independent supervisory authority* -

(1) An independent supervisory authority for the purposes of Article 51(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and the Council and Article 41 of Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and the Council is **the Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate**.

(2) In the performance of its functions, the Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate is independent and acts pursuant to this Act, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and the Council, other Acts and legislation established on the basis thereof.

4. Data subject's right to address Supervisory Authority. According to *Data Protection Act § 28* -

(1) If any data subject finds that the rights of the data subject are violated upon processing of personal data, the data subject has the right to address the Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate with a complaint.

(2) The Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate shall notify the data subject of the decision made based on the data subject's complaint and the right to have recourse to courts in order to contest the decision of the Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate.

(3) If a competent supervisory authority of another Member State of the European Union has jurisdiction in solving the complaint of the data subject, the Estonian Data Protection Inspectorate shall refer the data subject to the competent supervisory authority of the other Member State of the European Union for filing the complaint.

5. Data Protection Officer. No additional requirements are set out. Activities according to General Data Protection Regulation.

3.5.4 Data Protection Regulation in Latvia

1. Personal Data Processing Law. The purpose of this Personal Data Processing Law is to create legal preconditions for setting up of a system for the protection of personal data of a natural person at a national level by providing for the institutions necessary for such purpose, determining the competence and basic principles of operation thereof, as well as regulating operation of data protection officers and provisions of data processing and free movement [11].

2. Data Processing for Scientific Purposes. According to *Personal Data Processing Law Section 31. Data Processing for Scientific or Historical Research Purposes* – If data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes in the public interest, the rights of a data subject specified in Articles 15, 16, 18, and 21 of the Data Regulation shall not be applied, insofar as they may render impossible or seriously impair achievement of the specific purposes, and derogations are necessary for the achievement of such purposes.

3. Supervisory Authority. According to *Personal Data Processing Law Section 3 Data State Inspectorate* -

(1) The Data State Inspectorate is an institution of direct administration under the supervision of the Cabinet which is a data supervisory authority within the meaning of the Data Regulation and carries out the tasks in the area of data processing specified in the Data Regulation and this Law.

(2) The aim of the operation of the Inspectorate is to protect fundamental human rights and freedoms in the area of data protection.

(3) The Inspectorate shall be independent in the operation thereof.

4. Data subject's right to address Supervisory Authority.

No additional and special requirements are set out by Personal Data Processing Law. Activities according to General Data Protection Regulation.

5. Data Protection Officer. According to *Personal Data Processing Law Chapter 5* -

The controller or processor may appoint a person who, in accordance with the procedures laid down in this Law, has been included in the list of data protection officers of the Inspectorate, or another person as the data protection officer.

3.6 Main Legal Concerns

The main Legal Concerns are related to main research, technological and data protection legislation. European Union and national legislation determine the main framework within which the project will be carried out.

Not all legal issues may be unambiguous in the implementation of the project. Certain legal aspects may be subject to different interpretations by the participating partners. Therefore, it is important that the project partners treat the legal framework as consistently as possible. Protocols and guidelines for the processes developed help to create a common understanding of compliance with the legislation.

It is also important to define use-cases and trials as accurately as possible, factoring in the specific EU and national legal requirements.

In the case of research, the main subject is to carry it out in accordance with the rules laid down. Meeting the requirements for European projects is an important aspect here. The conduct of this research must comply with the requirements set out in the project conditions, which in turn are based on the requirements of Horizon 2020. Non-compliance with these requirements can significantly affect the implementation and results of the project. Misinterpretation of the legal aspects of research may result in financial or reputational damage.

Technological requirements are also important to follow. Non-compliance with technological conditions affects the implementation and results of the project.

Compliance with data processing and protection requirements is an important aspect of conducting research. Non-compliance with data processing and protection requirements may lead to project failure and damage both financially and reputationally.

4 Research Ethics Background

4.1 EU Research Ethics Background in H2020 projects

For all activities funded by the European Union, ethics is an integral part of research from start to end, and ethical compliance is seen as pivotal to achieve research excellence. According to the EC, “ethical research conduct implies the application of fundamental ethical principles and legislation to scientific research in all possible domains of research”¹. In the context of Horizon 2020 projects, this implies that “all the research and innovation activities carried out under Horizon 2020 shall comply with ethical principles and relevant national, Union and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocol. Particular attention shall be paid to the principle of proportionality, the rights of human participants and of the vulnerable population that may be implicated in the use cases, the right to privacy and to the protection of personal data, the right to non-discrimination and the need to ensure high levels of human health protection” [1].

4.1.1 Ethics Declarations and Conventions

5G-ROUTES Consortium partners confirm and commit to adhere to fundamental ethics principles and relevant national, European Union and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/c 364/01), the Convention of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data and especially Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) will be strictly followed when addressing the project’s ethical questions.

5G-ROUTES participating members are expected to conduct their research in keeping with article 8 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (protection of personal data). The remit of ethics and the scope of European values is broader than data protection and privacy alone. The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union applies a structure of six value domains, three of which warrant specific scrutiny in this project:

1. **Dignity**, notably individuals’ right to be secure in their physical and mental integrity.
2. **Freedoms**, comprising the rights to data protection and privacy, but also intellectual freedoms (education, expression, thought, religion and information) and social freedoms (assembly and property);
3. **Equality**, including non-discrimination and rights of minorities and of societally more vulnerable parties.

4.1.2 European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

In addition to the aforementioned ethical research principles, the consortium partners are also bound (art. 34 of the Grant Agreement) by the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity [12] which includes the following research integrity principles:

1. Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources;
2. Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full and unbiased way;
3. Respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment;
4. Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts.

¹ Horizon 2020 Online Manual, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/ethics_en.htm

It is the researchers' personal responsibility to carry out their research based on good research practice following the context described in the Code of Conduct in Research integrity covering:

1. Research Environment
2. Training, Supervision and Mentoring
3. Research Procedures
4. Safeguards
5. Data Practices and Management
6. Collaborative Working
7. Publication and Dissemination
8. Reviewing, Evaluating and Editing

For single researchers the safeguards shall be well known:

1. Researchers comply with codes and regulations relevant to their discipline.
2. Researchers handle research subjects, be they human, animal, cultural, biological, environmental or physical, with respect and care, and in accordance with legal and ethical provisions.
3. Researchers have due regard for the health, safety and welfare of the community, of collaborators and others connected with their research.
4. Research protocols take account of, and are sensitive to, relevant differences in age, gender, culture, religion, ethnic origin and social class.
5. Researchers recognise and manage potential harms and risks relating to their research.

Research is a process of inquiry. In the procedures or design phase of a research project, the researcher must examine the research plans potential ethical issues and take steps to correct them and must do so prior to contacting any participants.

The proposed research plan, and how it puts into practice, must survive ethical evaluation in advance; if an ethical problem exists, the researcher must modify the plan. Only when the plan can stand up to ethical challenges can the investigator to start or proceed to the next phase.

Ethical researchers must address the issues of explicit and informed consent, confidentiality, safety, deception, debriefing, security and diversity in their research with human participants. It is the task of researcher to think these issues through in order to find out whether the participants will experience and perhaps react negatively on any of these issues.

All partners of the consortium are fully committed and agree to collaborate for the fulfilment of their above-mentioned ethical responsibilities.

4.2 Gender perspective

4.2.1 Introduction

5G-ROUTES aim at embedding gender equality at each stage of the project. Over the years, the European Parliament has supported and called for measures to improve the position of women. This work continues through the activities of the Women's Committee. 5G-ROUTES aim at embedding gender equality at each stage of the project. The European Commission states that there are three objectives that underpin the strategy on gender equality in Horizon 2020²:

1. Fostering gender balance in research teams, in order to close the gaps in the participation of women;
2. Ensuring gender balance in decision-making, in order to reach the target of 40% of the under-represented sex in panels and groups and of 50% in advisory groups;

² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/promoting-gender-equality-research-and-innovation>

3. Integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation (R&I) content, helps improve the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology and/or innovation;

From a legal perspective, regulations and guidelines about gender equality in Horizon 2020 can be found in:

1. The Horizon 2020 Regulation [1];
2. The Rules for participation [13];
3. The Specific Programme implementing Horizon 2020 [14].

Moreover, the European Commission's Gender Roadmap Short guide defines a Gender Equality Plan as a set of actions aiming at:

1. Conducting impact assessment of procedures and practices to identify gender bias;
2. Identifying and implementing innovative strategies to correct any bias;
3. Setting targets and monitoring progress via indicators.

4.2.2 Implementation

The Grant Agreement states that beneficiaries “must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action” and “must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level”.

Considerations for gender balance in research teams should include:

1. Balanced representation of the genders in research and innovation activities to the possible extent as well as in management structures and research teams.
2. “Collective intelligence” meaning that no gender dominates over the other.
3. Balanced representation in decision-making.

5G-ROUTES includes **significant female representation**. 2 out of 8 work packages are led by females (WP4 by Liisi Koppel and WP5 by Jenny Rainbird (ILS)). Females represent 25% of the votes in the Project Management Board. Eight (8) tasks are also led or (co-)led by females, and prominent roles are held by females (Project Manager – Ioanna Fergadiotou (ILS), Quality Manager – Anaritta Leserri (ENIDE)). According to the current research team synthesis, one fourth of the votes in the General Assembly is thus allocated to females. The 5G-ROUTE reporting in the participant portal will include the percentage of women employed as researchers and/or participating in the project with other roles, which the European Commission can use as an indicator to monitor the implementation of gender balance measures in the project.

5G-ROUTES is committed to creating and sustaining a work environment that promotes equal opportunities across gender and that clearly prohibits discrimination. 5G-ROUTES supports equal career opportunities by:

- Making sure that working hour arrangements will not disproportionately disadvantage those with caring responsibilities;
- Having the Project Management Office regularly monitor issues related to gender, ranging from hiring to career opportunities and retention of staff.

As stated in 5G-ROUTES DoA, we will systematically analyse the relevance of sex/gender regarding the different expectations males and females may have towards 5G-ROUTES innovation. The innovation and the project will consider the gender dimension and will cater for the needs, motivations and differences between females and males where applicable. As part of the project, sex/gender analysis will be addressed with respect to:

1. The requirements analysis: A balanced participation of male and female professionals will allow gender analyses to be incorporated into the early user requirement definition. As per the recommendations of the European Institute for Gender Equality, we will sex-disaggregate the data to identify possible different expectations regarding the GUI interfaces, features, functionality, etc. based on sex/gender.

2. All steps of the technology enablers development: The GUI interface designs and ML algorithms (e.g. parameters) will be consulted with both males and females at different ages, and posterior alpha and beta versions will be trialled by both males and females. Gender differences of perception, understanding, cognition and reaction will be carefully considered in relation to the system's development.
3. The trials and evaluation of the results thereof: the possible usage of the innovation shall benefit males and females equally (as direct or indirect end-users). Behavioural specificities will be considered during the field trials and diversity and gender balance within end-user test groups will be ensured. The gender level of participation within the 5G-ROUTES activities will be monitored. Equal opportunities and equal treatment between men and women will be guaranteed.
4. 5G-ROUTES will ensure that during all its phases, and as much as possible equal gender participation will be maintained. This concerns both research, laboratory experiments and development phases, as well as the field-scale testing with the different use-cases. Gender dimension will be one of the field scale and other test/evaluations participants' characteristics that will be tracked in order to derive relevant conclusions, if possible and applicable.
5. The dissemination, communication and exploitation activities: gender will be considered and the gender-equality dimension promoted in the training, promotional and educational materials, in the target groups of the community building and outreach activities, as well as in the business models. This is essential for contributing to the education of the current professional and next generation of scientists, technologist and others needed in the EU to maximise its creativity and innovation potential. The dissemination and communication activities will promote the participation of female presenters in project workshops and in large-scale dissemination activities such as European and International Seminars and Conferences. Project achievements of female researchers and WP Leaders will be promoted via the project's website and social media acting as role models.

In addition, 5G-ROUTES will be vigilant in addressing the impact of the research in gender balance, although the proposed activities do not at this point imply to impact this dimension. In case that in the course of research such a potential impact is identified by a partner, then the attributes included in Table 2 should also be considered and reported (if relevant) in the respective deliverable.

Table 2. Issues to be reported in case gender is a factor that may affect research result outcomes

Attribute	Issues to specify / clarify
Research type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What type of research is appropriate for the investigation of the research hypothesis? • Is there a control group and how is it related to the original population sample?
Research protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there additional explanations/clarifications needed in relation to the gender? • How equivalent access/participation of all genders may be warranted?
Tool selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is there gender bias in the formulation of the questions?

Tool implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the examined gender categories comprehensive (e.g. in terms of examined cohorts) and relevant for the analysis? • Are the surveys/questionnaires acceptable for the targeted gender categories/
Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which method will be used to consider factors that may be influenced by the gender dimension?
Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do specific guidelines exist for reporting the gender dimension in the mean used for dissemination / reporting?

4.3 Ethical Aspects of Privacy

5G-ROUTES researchers will accordingly follow the appropriate ethics guidelines and rules for data handling and storage and informed consent procedures and participant recruitment criteria at their institution, in addition to national and EU legislation.

The entry into application of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) significantly raised the bar for the demonstration of compliance with ethical principles.

The general objective of Ethics policy is to ensure to compliance with ethics requirements. The central – but not exclusive – requirement relates to the processing of personal data in the course of the 5G-ROUTES project.

The right to data protection is a fundamental right as indicated in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and implies that any 5G-ROUTES use case where personal data is processed will need to adhere to applicable data protection law.

External inputs are mainly the GDPR, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, and the EU’s Responsible Research & Innovation policies.

Any ethics evaluation requires an explication of the normative framework against which the anticipated innovation is to be assessed. The central ethical concern is compliance with the fundamental right to data protection. The extent to which the project complies with European values as enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union – which includes, but is not limited to, the right to data protection and privacy includes specifically, Articles 7 and 8 that state:

- Article 7 (Respect for private and family life): Everyone has the right to respect for his or her private and family life, home and communications.
- Article 8 (Protection of personal data):
 - Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.
 - Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified.
 - Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority.

In relation to Article 7, the 5G-ROUTES project does not foresee any implication / infringement of private communications or other aspect of family life.

Management of data is addressed in D5.7 (“Data Management Plan v1.0” due on M06) and D5.8 (“Data Management Plan final version” due on M33) as part of T5.3 - Innovation, data management and IPR activities which might include a Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) as per Article 35 of the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/67, in accordance with herein Section 6.4.2.3. The DMP will fully comply with the proposed protocols as described in the current deliverable and define the management strategies to be applied during the

data processing procedures in the project. As such, the DMP will be updated in M33 with decisions upon the data categories to be shared outside the consortium and the selected formats of these based on the information obtained and the personal data processing performed in the Use Cases so as to fully abide by the GDPR provisions.

In relation to Article 8, the information sheets, informed consent forms and informed consent procedures as herein described in Section 6, in conjunction with the approvals obtained from the partner's DPOs and the safeguards implemented by the Data Controller (in agreement with Art. 24 of the GDPR) and the Data Processor(s) (in agreement with Art. 28 of the GDPR) for the processing of personal data and the adequacy of the relevant DPIAs will provide the appropriate safeguard for compliance of the 5G-ROUTES with it.

In relation to the aforementioned, privacy is the protection of the person's physical, mental and behavioural sharing of oneself. Confidentiality is how researchers should treat the participant's information and ensure that no private information or other type of data is disclosed without written consent by the participant. The treatment of information that an individual has disclosed in a relationship of trust and with the expectation that it will not be divulged to others without permission or in ways that are inconsistent with the understanding of the original disclosure (in informed consent documents).

Personal data might be only temporarily recorded according to the GDPR and they will be deleted if the participant wishes so. Important aspects of data protection that are accommodated for in the consent form are the following:

- Data collection, storage and research purpose
- Data transfer and communication
- Data ownership
- Data connection with personal information and separate storage
- Commercial exploitation of data
- Data storage duration
- Granting access to data
- Data supervision

In addition, the DPM shall also include the '*Privacy Policy*' which will explain in detail how the consortium processes personal data and how it applies personal data protection principles in accordance with the detailed instructions provided in articles 12, 13 and 14 of the GDPR, placing an emphasis on making them easy to understand and accessible and by following recommended by the EC templates³. According to the GDPR, the consortium must provide people with a privacy policy (or privacy note) that is:

- In a concise, transparent, intelligible, and easily accessible form.
- Written in clear and plain language, particularly for any information addressed specifically to a child.
- Delivered in a timely manner.
- Provided free of charge.

Thus, the privacy ethics issues relate to the personal data privacy and protection as summarized per WP in next Section 4.4.1. A preliminary risk identification and proposed mitigation strategy has been provided in Section 6.2.2 and will be thoroughly complemented, as aforementioned, by relevant DPIAs.

³ <https://gdpr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Our-Company-Privacy-Policy.pdf>

4.4 Main Ethics Concerns

4.4.1 Ethics requirements

The 5G-ROUTES project will conduct advanced field trials of the most representative and innovative Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) applications seamlessly functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor ('Via Baltica-North') spanning across 3 European Union member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G-based interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe. It aims at validating 5G as a true enabler of innovative CAM services that cannot be realized by today's wireless communication technologies (e.g. 4G LTE, IEEE 802.11p) due to stringent technical requirements. This will be achieved through a diverse set of 13 use cases that span beyond C-ITS, covering the automotive, railway and shipping sectors that are expected to have the highest commercialisation and social potential. The use cases are grouped in 5 categories (i.e. automated cooperative driving, awareness driving, sensing driving, uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go and multimodal services) covering applications in the context of complete connectivity-enabled ecosystems around passengers and cargo.

In particular, the use cases combine at one leg either automotive or railway transport and on the other multimodal transport including shipping. To do so, the 5G-ROUTES consortium works directly with various actors: MNOs, telecom vendors, satellite operator, vehicle manufacturers and suppliers, railway and shipping operators, SMEs, academia and researchers. Consequently, in 5G-ROUTES, the ethics requirements imposed from the ethics screening report refer to the involvement of human beings in the research process, and the processing of personal data throughout the project's lifetime as following:

- Ethics requirement D8.1: H - Requirement No. 1 as imposed by the DoA (Annex 1, part A) and relevant to the human participants, relevant procedures, criteria and informed consent/assent forms. Due on M06.
- Ethics requirement D8.2: H - Requirement No. 2 as imposed by the DoA (Annex 1, part A) and relevant to provisions set in the GDPR 2016/679 for the protection and privacy of personal data processed during the project. Due on M06.

EEE is the lead partner responsible for the delivery of the aforementioned requirements under the advisory of the Ethics Panel (EP), described in the next section, the supervision of Mr. Henri Schasmin's (TTU) and the Academic Ethics Committee of TTU who will review and approve the ethical requirements of the project.

Table 3 summarizes the WPs where such involvement is foreseen and the relevant approvals that must be obtained.

Table 8 in Annex I provides the details for the human participation activities identified in Table 3.

Table 3. Human participation and data privacy and protection ethical issues identified

WP/Task	Ethics issue
Human participation: research activity involving humans	
WP1 (T1.1; T1.4)	Questionnaires and focus group for use case requirements and specifications.

WP2 (T2.2)	Dry-run interworking tests will be performed that might also include human participants to verify proper operation, functionality and interoperability prior to live deployment in large-scale field trials
WP3 (T3.4)	Lab-trials (test-beds) will be conducted that will also include human participants to assess the performance of the network and the CAM ecosystem and technically validate the proper operation of the use cases in lab environments
WP4 (T4.2; T4.3)	Large-scale field trials (use cases) with human participation also that will involve automated test vehicles, end-user devices and CAM applications, and in some cases passengers. In some Use cases the participation of vulnerable population is foreseen (see Use Case 3.3 description in Section 5.2.4)
WP5 (T5.2)	Conference calls / Interviews with targeted standardization community and consortium members training sessions (e.g. on IPR and patents).
WP6 (T6.1; T6.2; T6.3)	Dissemination and communication activities including Tutorials, PhD schools, focus group workshops, scientific workshops
Personal data privacy and protection	
WP1-WP6	All activities involving human participation have the potential to process personal data (herein by 'process' we also refer to the collection as per the GDPR definition). Although the Ethics and security section (DoA, Annex 1, Part B) clearly mentions that <i>"For what concerns data related to individuals participating in project workshops, events, interviews and trials, as a general rule, only anonymised or aggregated data (completely disjoined from people identification and profiles) will be processed. Organisational and technical mechanisms for the anonymisation and encryption of any personal data to be logged in the various systems at the trials site facilities will be adopted."</i> , in case the data was not anonymous at the time of the collection (e.g. collecting data 'anonymously' and of such nature that these may not indirectly lead to the identification of a person), they still pertain to the provision of the GDPR for data protection and privacy. In any case, as cameras will be installed and recording in large-scale field trials, there is the potential of collecting data leading to person localization (e.g. through license plate identification)
WP3-4	In addition to the aforementioned, network measurement techniques, such as IPFIX and DPI might include some personal information, such as total network usage and specific applications used, which can be inferred through source IP and MAC addresses. For such cases, as anonymising or masking such information will render it unsuitable for the analysis of tools and algorithms, the consortium partners have committed to use pseudonymisation techniques. These should be detailed in the relevant

	versions of the DMP (D5.7 and D5.8) due in M06 and M33 respectively under T5.3 – Innovation, data management and IPR activities (eBOS).
WP6	Communication and dissemination activities using web-based communication means may also potentially process personal data (e.g. from two-way access between online social media sites between the consortium partners and the technical and public audience; on-line video clips and surveys).

4.4.2 Compliance with health and safety (H&S) procedures and other ethics issues

During the 5G-ROUTES project, three (3) test-beds and 13 Use Cases in large-scale field trials will be performed with humans (i.e. researchers and volunteers) participating in trial testing and at public locations. These pilots will include the testing of automated vehicles using advanced 5G functionalities based on V2V and V2X communications and LIDAR detection systems, thus enabling at least level 3 automation.

The partners must ensure that the appropriate Health and Safety (H&S) procedures for the researchers (staff of consortium partners) as well as for external research participants (drivers, non-drivers) on departmental/institutional but also on regional/national level are followed and appropriate training is administered. In particular, with respect to the provisions of the following relevant EU Directives:

1. Framework Directive 89/331/EC for the safety and health of workers at work.
2. Directive 2009/104/EC on the use of work equipment.
3. Directive 2013/35/EU on the minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (electromagnetic fields). Specifically, Directive 2013/35/EU provisions for relevant risk assessments, as per the precautionary principle, when certain exposure conditions are met.

Moreover, when legally required, authorisations for the testing of automated vehicles in real traffic conditions must be obtained from the relevant authorities. Physical risks stemming from traffic safety issues shall also be considered. The provisional overview of the respective H&S guidelines/legislation/protocols for the 5G-ROUTES test sites is provided in Annex II. This overview will be stored in the online collaboration platform in folder WP7/T7.4, will remain as a live document, and will be annexed in D7.8 on M35.

It is up to each partner responsible for each pilot site, testbed and Use Case site to follow the provisions of the aforementioned directives and identify and follow other H&S institutional protocols and traffic safety provisions that may be applicable and inform the Ethics Panel about the respective protocols.

In addition, a supplementary ethical issue could be the respect of principles and key requirements outlined in the “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence”⁴ should the 5G-ROUTES project consider AI supported operational infrastructure. To be considered trustworthy, the development of such infrastructure must be:

1. Lawful - respecting all applicable laws and regulations.
2. Ethical - respecting ethical principles and values.
3. Robust - both from a technical perspective while taking into account its social environment.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

5 5G-ROUTES Research Process Overview

5.1 Project Purpose

5G-ROUTES seeks to accelerate the acceptance of CAM for fully autonomous, safer, cleaner, more traffic efficient, more user friendly and reliable mobility, as well as for seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable cross-border CAM services. This will be empowered by ubiquitous 5G coverage and by large-scale deployment of CAM in all urban areas and along main transport paths throughout Europe.

5G-ROUTES has carefully targeted the strategically important 'Via Baltica-North' 5G EU corridor for large-scale CAM field trials that involve road, rail and maritime modes of transport, covering Latvia and Estonia and extending it to Finland via the Gulf of Finland.

To achieve the above, 5G-ROUTES will field trial a diverse set of 13 use cases that span beyond C-ITS, covering the automotive, infotainment and transport & logistics sectors, including railway and shipping. The use cases cover applications in the context of complete connectivity-enabled ecosystems around passengers and cargo. They combine on one hand either automotive and/or railway transport and on the other, multimodal transport (including shipping).

In particular, 5G-ROUTES will include:

- 13 advanced, commercially exploitable use cases;
- Definition of at least 150 key 5G target technical, service-level and business related KPIs;
- Initial lab trials;
- Large-scale field trials:
 - First, localized large-scale trials at strategic locations, i.e. Valga city located on the borders of Estonia and Latvia, in Tallinn and in the Gulf of Finland between Tallinn and Helsinki ports over 3GPP Release 16 (R.16) and then over R.17;
 - Second, larger-scale trials over R.17 leveraging the 5G upgraded networks of the MNOs (i.e. LMT in Latvia, TELIA in Estonia/Finland) covering significant portions of the roads, railway tracks and ship lines along the entire 'Via Baltica-North' 5G corridor. Satellite 5G connectivity, provided by AIRBUS will be complemented and integrated with terrestrial 5G coverage to demonstrate 5G service continuity, especially in challenging/remote/underserved areas.

5G-ROUTES will leverage the KPI visualisation system of the previous 5G-SOLUTIONS project and extend its functionality to incorporate the CAM use cases, thus enabling the parallel execution of use cases, automating the analysis and presentation of the results obtained from the trials and presenting them through an intuitive user-friendly dashboard in near-real time.

The above will provide the flexibility for the system to adapt to new interfaces, data sources, GDPR compliant data processing, machine learning and representation requirements. An essential component of the KPI visualization system for achieving GDPR compliance is the "Pseudo-anonymization: data anonymization based on GDPR compliance".

What follows presents more details about the research process and methods conducted in 5G-ROUTES, based on work-in-progress deliverables D1.1 ("Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0") and D1.7 ("Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0 Interim (v1.0) of reports"), as well as the project DoA.

5.2 Research Process

In 5G-ROUTES, individuals might be involved in human participation related to interviews, surveys, events where personal data will be collected and various testing (test-beds/use cases). This and other related issues are to be addressed as per the research process described in what follows.

5.2.1 External Advisory Board and Ethics Panel

The 5G-ROUTES' project management structure includes the support of two bodies that are of particular relevance to the legal and ethical aspects: 1) of an External Advisory Board (EAB) and 2) of an Ethics Panel (EP).

5.2.1.1 External Advisory Board (EAB)

The EAB comprises a well-balanced group of external "advisors" drawn from across Europe and embracing a range of knowledge of the project's focus areas. The EAB will offer impartial external advice from technological, scientific, market, regulation, ethical, societal, economic and business points of view.

Role and mission of the EAB

The major function of the EAB will be to validate the technology direction proposed by the consortium. It will be chaired by one of its members, elected upon the first meeting of the EAB in month M06. Consultations of the EAB will be on an ad-hoc basis. The EAB will also be convened at a project meeting (in M06, M18 & M36 synchronized with the relevant GA and review meetings) to be presented with the 5G-ROUTES' progress, decisions and designs, in relation to which they will provide their opinion and possible further guidance. In turn, the consortium will take into account the received feedback in order to rectify, if necessary, or to implement relevant aspects as indicated by the EAB. The EAB's suggestions and relevant decisions will be reported in the Minutes of the respective meetings.

Composition of the EAB

The EAB's composition has been established in the DoA. Table 4 lists the seven (7) persons who have explicitly confirmed their interest and willingness to participate in 5G-ROUTES' EAB and includes their short profile.

Table 4. EAB member composition and short profile

Name & Position	Short profile
Džineta Innusa (F): Acting State Secretary, Ministry of Transport, Republic of Latvia.	Džineta Innusa is the Acting State Secretary at the Ministry of Transport in Latvia. Džineta holds a Master of Law from the Latvijas Universitate. She works at the Ministry of Transport for more than 9 years, always dedicated to the Ministry's mission to elaborate and implement the state policy of Latvia in the fields of transport and communications; maintain and develop an effective, safe, competitive, environment friendly and flexible transport system which offers vast opportunities to the users of this system and also create a liberalised and harmonious legal and economic environment of the communication sector in accordance with the demands of the EU providing effective and rational utilization of natural resources, promoting competitiveness and attracting investments.
Ahti Kuningas (M): Deputy Secretary General for Transport, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, Estonia.	Ahti Kuningas, the Deputy Secretary General for Transport coordinates the development, implementation and surveillance of transportation development plans within the Ministry's area of government. The Deputy Secretary General is in charge of the development and implementation

	of operational programmes that support transportation development, emergency plans, target programmes and foreign aid projects.
<p>Eetu Pilli-Sihvola, (M): Chief Adviser – Connected and Automated Driving, Finnish Transport and Communications Agency Traficom, Finland.</p>	<p>Eetu Pilli-Sihvola is the Chief Adviser on Connected and Automated Vehicles at the Finnish Transport and Communications Agency Traficom. He has worked both in research and government in the field of Intelligent Transport Systems and transportation for 10+ years. Eetu has been involved in a number of H2020 research projects and proposal preparations, both as a participant and as an adviser. His main areas of expertise are foresight for new mobility innovations, impacts of connected and automated vehicles on the transport system and the role of cities and authorities, and project management.</p>
<p>Delphine Bernet-Travert (F): Secretary General, Independent Regulators Group (IRG), Brussels.</p>	<p>Delphine is the Head of the Independent Regulators Group (IRG) Secretariat in Brussels, which was established in 1997 as a group of European National Telecommunications Regulatory Authorities (NRAs) to share experiences and points of views among its members on important issues relating to the regulation and development of the European telecommunications market. Delphine is a Senior Brussels-based lobbyist with Project management skills and more than 10 years' experience in EU and Public & Government Affairs including communication. Her specific areas of expertise are focused in various sectoral policies of the EU (Regional/Interregional cooperation, Agriculture, Telecoms, External Relations and Development, EU Industrial Policy, EU 2020).</p>
<p>Valdo Kalm (M): Chairman of the Management Board, Port of Tallinn, Estonia.</p>	<p>Mr. Valdo Kalm is a top executive and public figure in Estonia. He has been Chairperson of the Management Board and CEO of Port of Tallinn since 2016. Prior to this role, he was the Chairperson of the Board of telephony operator Elion Enterprises from 2000 to 2003, and Chairperson of the Board of mobile operator EMT from 2003 to 2014. He was also the Chairperson of the Management Board of Eesti Telekom (now Telia Estonia) from 2007 to 2016. He received the 3rd class Order of the White Star recognition in 2014 for services rendered to the Estonian State.</p>
<p>Pekka Meronen (M): Vice President, Finance, ICT and Development, Port of Helsinki, Finland.</p>	<p>Mr. Pekka is the VP Finances, ICT and Development at the Port of Helsinki. Mr. Pekka is an Experienced Finance/Administrative Director with a demonstrated history of working in the logistics and maritime industry in both Private and Public sector. He is a strong professional with a Master of Science (MSc) focused in Industrial Management and Engineering from Tampere University of Technology. In his current position his responsibilities</p>

	<p>include: Finances, administration, ICT, legal matters, sustainability and corporation matters. He previously served as a CT-Logistics Oy Development and Finances Director (2012–2014); as an Administrative Director at the Port of Rauma (2003–2012) and as a Project Manager at the Port of Kotka (2000–2003). Mr. Pekka held the following positions of trust: Board member of South Finland Port Services; Board member of Port of Loviisa; Board member of Metropolilab Oy; Board member of Logistics Research and Promotion Foundation. Board member (2013 – 2015) and vice chairman (2014 –2015) of Finnish Association of Purchasing and Logistics LOGY ry; Board member of LIMOWA Logistics Centre Cluster 2012–2014.</p>
<p>Hanno Lindpere (M): Head of Transaction and Advisory services, KPMG Baltics OÜ, Estonia;</p>	<p>Hanno joined KPMG in 2015 leading KPMG Transaction & Advisory department and his main task is management of major projects. His areas of expertise include strategic planning, modelling, organization analysis, process mapping, due diligence, transaction advisory services etc. Hanno has strong communication skills, extensive leadership experience and highly efficient project management and co-ordination skills. He also specializes in retail, infrastructure sectors et al. and has carried out multiple engagements including carve-outs of real-estate portfolios, PPPs, feasibility studies. He is part of the global infrastructure team, and has carried out multiple assignments for major Estonian infrastructure assets. He has over 20 years of experience in advisory and audit services.</p>

5.2.1.2 Ethics Panel (EP)

The Description of Action (DoA) – Part B, foresees the creation of an Ethics Panel (EP). The responsibilities and structure of the EB in relation to Ethics is discussed in this sub-section.

Role and mission of the EP

Compliance of the 5G-ROUTES project research activities with ethical standards and guidelines will be further ensured through the establishment of the EP of experts. The latter will monitor all legal, gender and ethics-related aspects in the project and will consult the project consortium on the relevant potential impacts of the activities undertaken. The EP is necessary to ensure critical appraisal of the legal, ethical and gender issues arising from the activities of the project, especially as the project aims to process personal data, as well as involve human participants in a number of activities (i.e. surveys, questionnaires, testbeds and use cases).

The following Deliverables will be drafted in consultation with the EP, acting as supervisors of the ethical activities of the project and considering both European and national ethical and legal requirements, as these will include the Ethics and Data protection and privacy policies of the project and relevant procedures, assessments if needed and informed consent/assent forms:

- Ethics requirement D8.1: H - Requirement No. 1 as imposed by the DoA (Annex 1, part A) and relevant to the human participants, relevant procedures, criteria and informed consent/assent forms. Due on M06.
- Ethics requirement D8.2: H - Requirement No. 2 as imposed by the DoA (Annex 1, part A) and relevant to provisions set in the GDPR 2016/679 for the protection and privacy of personal data processed during the project. Due on M06.
- D7.8 'Report on legal and ethics monitoring final version'. Due on M35.
- Initial and Final version of the Data Management Plans on M6 and M33 (deliverable D5.7 and D5.8).

The aforementioned deliverables will also summarize the activities of the EP. As per the DoA (Annex 1, part A), the Academic Ethics Committee of TTU will review and approve the deliverables concerning the ethics requirements of the project. More specifically, Mr Henri Schasmin (TTU) will also act as the 5G-ROUTES's Data Protection Officer (DPO) and will collaborate with partners' assigned Data Privacy Single Point of Contact, supporting them during the research process to comply with ethical principles and the legal framework on privacy as well as maintaining track of partners activity for what concern local authorities' notifications and requests for authorisation when needed.

The EP will scrutinize the research and the activities of the project undertaken in its lifetime, and its role is to:

1. Ensure that the project's research conforms to the highest ethical standards as these were presented in Sections 3 and 4;
2. Monitor the objectives, legal and ethical and gender implications of the project's research and oversee the ethics approval processes at project level.
3. Provide guidelines for the protection of private information.
4. Advise project participants on how to address ethical and data protection issues, including ethics issues related to automation as necessary and mitigate risks.
5. Assist in resolving any potential ethics related conflicts.
6. Ensure that the relevant health and safety measures for the researchers and research participants and the environment (e.g. other vehicles/ transport modes / or pedestrians in the field test vicinity that may be affected) are taken into consideration when testing technologies are considered (i.e. test beds and use cases).
7. Ensure that partners have obtained the necessary authorisations for the implementation of the field trials (Use cases) and/or other human participation related activity by the competent authority in the responsible partner's country or, alternatively, from their own internal Ethics Committee.
8. Facilitate the collaboration with external members (e.g. regional /municipality authorities) to ensure the EP is making decisions that are in harmony with the legal and ethical profile and agenda of the areas that will act as field sites. The aforementioned responsibility falls primarily to the EP member from the partner that originates from the respective country (ies) where the field tests will be performed. They will be the main contact point for any ethics related issues (e.g. submission of research/test protocols for approval, by the Institutional/National Ethics Committees, GDPR, etc.) from the pilot site point of view. Any required or requested authorisations and approvals remain official project documents at any time, will be stored in the online collaboration platform in folder WP7/T7.4, and will be annexed in D7.8 on M35. In relation to this,
9. Table 8 provided in Annex I and Table 9 in Annex II (concerning the testbeds and use cases) should be updated by the EP members and remain live documents so as to know when activities are actually performed, by which partners, whom (i.e. human participants) will these involve and the respective H&S measures and guidelines to follow. For the large scale field pilots (use cases), it is the responsibility of the EP member of the partner responsible of the activity to make sure that this is uploaded and properly filled out with the respective information together with the following separate documents in English: the **Ethics Checklist Form** (see Annex III) and the Ethics Controlling Report (see Annex IV).
10. Review and evaluate the necessary documents according to the project schedule. Specifically:
 - a. Review information provided in the aforementioned live

- b. Table 8 (Annex I) and Table 9 (Annex II) and ensure that these are properly filled out.
 - c. Review the Ethics Checklist form prior to the performance of testbeds and use cases and ensure that is properly completed.
 - d. Review any deliverable (submitted or in the drafting process) they may deem to be of relevance to legal, ethics and gender issues in case there is rising concern in relation to these.
11. Respect participant's free will and treat them as intelligent beings who decide for themselves about any type of data processed that are indeed outcomes of their participation.
 12. Communicate any relevant issues to the Project Management Board (as per DoA, Annex 1, Part B) to ensure these issues will be timely and effectively addressed, managed and resolved.
 13. Modify and amend the Ethics policy and protocols in case unforeseen legal or ethics issues arise or create substantial difficulties in the implementation of the relevant protocols, following written notification to the Project Management Board and the DG-CNECT PO responsible for the project and after obtaining written approvals by them.

Thus, the Consortium shall implement the research project in full respect of the legal and ethical national requirements and code of practice.

The members of the EP may raise any ethical or legal issue related to the 5G-ROUTES project and must be consulted at least on the ethical and legal issues raised in the ethics screening report and the imposed aforementioned requirements.

It is planned that the EP will have at least 2 main remote meetings by teleconference. However, members of the EP are free to organise supplementary meetings in accordance with legal and ethical issues that may arise during the implementation of the project (ad hoc meetings or task/issue specific meetings on a need to do basis).

The EP will also convene at the meetings involving the EAB (i.e. M06, M18 and M36) so as to be informed about the project progress and also provide their opinion and possible further guidance in relation to potential research direction. The EP will also convene before the final planning of the solution and the use case demonstration of the 5G lab environment (starting in M09) to ensure that all ethical issues are properly taken into account. The EP's suggestions and relevant decisions will be reported in the Minutes of the respective meetings.

Composition of the EP

In 5G-ROUTES, the EP is chaired by the Legal & Ethics Leader. Mr. Henri Schasmin (TTU) and includes legal advisors of the participating members (experts on ethics, privacy, gender and legal issues). The EP is formed of the respective representatives of the participating members.

These members will be designated on the basis of proven expertise and qualification in the fields of law or ethics. The selection of the members of the EP shall be based on the following principles included in Table 5.

Table 5. Required expertise for members of the Ethics Panel

Legal requirements	Professional requirements	Competence requirements	Educational requirements
Representative of the participating member with a valid contract (employment contract, etc.).	The performance of the duties has been related to research and development. Priority shall be given to persons that are also involved in test-beds and field testing	1. Previous experience in technology projects.	Higher education, at least a master's degree.

	activities.	2. Previous experience with project ethics. 3. Previous experience with legal and data protection issues.	
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Relevant consortium partners have suggested a qualified member to join the panel accompanied by a CV and approved first by the panel chair. Table 6. Ethics Panel members, research activity with humans and required opinions/approvals hereunder lists the proposed EP members by the partners, the research activity involving participation of humans by the partners and the ethics opinions and or approvals that are required (from national/local authorities and/or Partner's Ethics Committees).

Table 6. Ethics Panel members, research activity with humans and required opinions/approvals

Partner	Ethics Panel Member	Research activity involving humans	Opinions / approvals by ethics committees and /or competent authorities
PV	Ojārs Rozenbergs	No	Internal Ethics standards
ATOS	Elisa Jimeno	No	TBD
BRA	Francisco Ibañez	To be identified	TBD
eBOS	Christos Skoufis	To be identified	EBOS has no Ethics Committee. Christos Skoufis will support this aspect.
EDI	Kaspars Ozols	To be identified	EDI has no Ethics Committee. Kaspars Ozols will provide support related to ethical issues.
CERTH	Katerina Toulou	To be identified	CERTH has an Ethics Committee. The administrative contact person for the Ethics Committee is Ms. Fotini, Kopani (kopani@certh.gr). In

			communications, please also cc Stella Nikolaou (snikol@certh.gr) and Katerina Toulou (touliouk@certh.gr) for follow up purposes.
ILS	Jenny Rainbird	WP5 activities	N/A
LMT	Edite Stipra (TBC)	No plans	LMT does not have an Ethics Committee. Ethical issues are integrated through internal manuals and procedures according to ISO quality standards.
SWM	Josè Rodriguez	No plans	Swarco supports ethics and integrity principles through internal manuals.
TTU	Henri Schasmin (Chair of the Ethics Panel)	No plans	TTU has an Academic Ethics Committee. The Committee of TTU will review and approve the ethical requirements of the project. The current Ethics Committee is chaired by prof Tanel Kerikmäe (tanel.kerikmae@taltech.ee). The contact person is Mr. Henri Schasmin (henri.schasmin@taltech.ee)
VTT	Johan Scholliers	No plans	VTT has an Ethics Committee, which will be contacted if needed.
TELIA	Anette Soosaar	No plans	
VED	Sarah Duclos	UC3.3. Possibly It can be using anonymous questionnaires	VEDECOM has conducted such experiments in previous projects. A consent form is provided to the human factors experiments informing the participants about the collected data and its usage. and all the data logging follows GDPR guidelines and is anonymized

VEDIA	Lasse Nykänen	Use Case 4, where Vedia will participate via its Vedia Claus application and smartphones. At this point aim is to use Vedia staff for connectivity tests, because of COVID restrictions	Vedia does not have an Ethics Committee; however, ethics issues are integrated to our company code of conduct and quality process
WINGS	Aikaterini Iliana Kofidou	Use case 5.2 which addresses multimodal mobility may require the tracking of the location of human experimenters (through their smartphone) and/or the license plate recognition of incoming vehicles	Such experiments have been conducted in previous projects by us. A clear and understandable consent form is provided to the human experimenters informing them about the data to be logged. Data logging follows GDPR guidelines and is anonymized to protect the privacy of the human experimenters

Table 6 will be continuously updated by the EP members and remain a live document for reference, stored in the online collaboration platform in folder WP7/T7.4, and annexed in D7.8 on M35. The Chair of the EP should be notified in case a partner wishes to substitute its EP member and approve accordingly.

5.2.2 Testbeds and test sites

1) CTTC 5G Testbeds (Barcelona): A 5G testbed based on OpenAirInterface 5G and ETSI OSM MANO stack will be provided by CTTC, which leverages a Cloud Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture, with a 5G core and a fully virtualised 5G RAN and an optical/wireless Fronthaul.

2) TTU 5G Testbeds (Tallinn): 1) the 5G-IoT testbed “DORM” located at TalTech campus including 50 end-user enabled devices with NB-IoT modules and sensors, a 5G base station manufactured by Ericsson and commercially operated by TELIA and a cloud platform for data analysis and predictive algorithms. 2) 5G D2D SideLink testbed: comprises of multi-hop D2D communication based on open source OpenAirInterface (OAI).

3) VTT 5G test site (Tampere): VTT's test site in Finland is extended until the Tampere region (at the end of the "Via Baltica-North" 5G corridor), where the specific test site enables automated driving subsystem experiments against the commercial network in the 5G corridor. The test site has 10 base stations which will be upgraded to support 5G functionality, operating at 2,6 GHz band. In addition, VTT has its own specific trailer with Intrinsync CV2X devices implemented in the 5,9 GHz band. VTT is using their Large Research Infrastructure (LRI) facilities for validating the use case technical and service-level KPIs.

4) Test site (Rīga): "Bīķernieki" racetrack will be used by EDI & LMT for the project to perform local trials as well as alternative way for cross border trials, where network "Handover" and "Handshake" scenarios will be tackled along with Telia MNO. Test site will be used to conduct experiments for UC1.1, UC1.2. UC2.2. as well to perform validation of these use cases. Riga "Bīķernieki".

5.2.3 Trials

During the project, each use case will deploy a layered testing practice to drive development, involving significant industry representative tests, verifications and validations. Two types of large-scale trials will be conducted:

1) Localised large-scale trials in the "Via Baltica North" 5G corridor aiming at localised validation of 5G enabling technologies' features and capabilities in the cross-border areas (i.e. Valga, Tallinn and Helsinki ports). Some advanced 5G functionalities, such as 5G NR and extreme coverage in commercially available 5G nodes will be deployed by the MNOs and their preferred vendors in these concentrated cross-border areas. In total, 12 commercial 5G RAN MEC-enabled nodes will be installed from Q1 2021 in 3 pilot sites (1 in Helsinki port, 2 in Tallinn port area and 6 in Valga city traversing Estonia and Latvia) as well as 1 in ships and 2 in railway wagons. In addition, two experimental RAN MEC-enabled nodes will be provided by CTTC in railway wagons to emulate private 5G networks in rail networks.

2) Wider larger scale trials validating 5G enabling technologies' features and capabilities in significant portions of motorways, railways and shipways along the "Via Baltica North" 5G corridor. For this purpose, the existing LTE networks of TELIA in Estonia and in Finland as well as of LMT in Latvia will be upgraded to support 5G connectivity along major cities and motorways in these countries. In areas where terrestrial 5G connectivity might not be available, satellite 5G connectivity provided by AIRBUS will ensure CAM service continuity whilst satisfying the requirements of the CAM use cases related to the eMBB, URLLC and mMTC service classes.

5.2.4 Use Cases

1) Use Case Category 1: Automated Cooperative Driving

- Use Case 1.1: Dynamic vehicles platooning. Scenario type: V2V combined with mMTC and URLLC. The goal is to enable vehicles to dynamically form a group travelling together and very close to each other. Automated vehicles driving together, dynamically form a group, moving at a very close distance from each other at harmonised speeds following a piloting vehicle. All vehicles in the platoon receive periodic data from the leading vehicle, in order to enable their AI-based OBUs to carry on platoon operations based on V2V communications and LIDAR detection system or environment perception system, thus enabling at least level 3 automation. This information allows the distance between vehicles to become extremely small (less than 5 meters), implying that the gap distance translated to time is in the order of a few tens of milliseconds for vehicles platooning at speeds allowed to drive at the given testing path section in cross-border highways, fulfilling safety requirements. Therefore, the OBU should be able to make calculations and apply them through MEC-enabled RAN stations at ultra-low latencies (i.e. less than 5ms with less than 10% jitter). Only the driver of the leading vehicle remains responsible for steering (level 1 automation), whereas the drivers in the following vehicles are relieved from driving, i.e. from both steering, accelerating, decelerating and maintaining the same distance (level 4 automation).
- Use Case 1.2: Cooperative lane change. Scenario type: V2V combined with mMTC and URLLC. The goal is to perform joint manoeuvre decisions and coordinate driving trajectories amongst a group of vehicles, in order to enhance the safety and help the vehicles getting through difficult traffic situations: As part of

the automated driving tasks, a vehicle should be able to apply maneuvers in an automated manner, e.g. automatically change lanes in highways or at testing ground with required conditions when appropriate, fulfilling safety requirements. For this, the interaction with the surrounding and the cooperation with other vehicles in the vicinity is of absolute importance, especially in the case of blind spots. The relative speed information of nearby vehicles is also considered to determine the risk factor and appreciate the safety of the maneuver, to avoid lateral or/and rear collisions with other passing vehicles. All nearby vehicles are informed about the intentions of the vehicle to perform safe lane change and reduce their speeds.

- Use Case 1.3: See-Through view for safe automated overtake. Scenario type: V2V, V2N combined with eMBB, mMTC and URLLC. The goal is to provide enhanced visibility of road awareness for safe automated overtake in order to prevent catastrophic head-on collisions during an automated overtake manoeuvre. In many occasions, the visibility of a vehicle may be obscured by elements in the scene, e.g. pedestrian crossing in front of a vehicle. In this use case, which is an example of an advanced driving assistance application, long vehicles in platoons share video images of road conditions ahead of them to vehicles behind them. The driver, sitting in an automated vehicle, makes a decision and informs his/her vehicle to overtake the preceding long vehicle but does not have a clear view for a safe overtake. See-Through helps the automated vehicle to take informed decisions, based on the information received (e.g. real-time UHD video feed from the vehicle in front, taking into consideration a number of parameters including potential hazards, such as an oncoming remote vehicle in the passing lane or a lack of room in front of the leading remote vehicle) for a safe overtake without the engagement of the driver.

1) Use Case Category 2: Awareness Driving

- Use Case 2.1: Real-time traffic information and cooperative intersection collision control. Scenario type: V2V, V2I, V2N combined with eMBB, mMTC and URLLC. The goal is to provide enhanced real-time traffic visual monitoring and control of intersection traffic for cooperative automated driving for safe passing and avoiding collisions with other vehicles and VRUs. An intelligent AI-based Intersection Controller System (ICS) installed at the intersection, enables both the detection and prevention of potential collisions in real-time as well as more efficient operation of the intersection by notifying approaching vehicles about signal phase and timing, dynamically instructing them to adjust their speed and coordinates the traffic flow according to the actual traffic conditions. The ICS consists of road radar, traffic signal, Road Side Units (RSU), 360o UHD elevated cameras overlaid with geolocation-based information to provide enhanced situational awareness and augmented reality-based navigation to approaching vehicles and a controller server in the MEC or cloud, in which local digital dynamics map information is stored. The controller server data can be downloaded into the vehicles' OBU either periodically or on demand, so that vehicles can be informed about the status of the intersection situation at any time and provided with relevant instructions for cooperative intersection collision control. The ICS continuously monitors and gathers traffic data at the intersection, such as traffic signals, vehicle types and speeds, geolocation, trajectories, accelerations/decelerations, etc. Then, the ICS integrates and synchronises temporal traffic data from its constituent components and feeds them to the controller server which subsequently processes the data, calculates the trajectories of the vehicles and the Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) and instructs the automated vehicles to automatically adjust their speeds and trajectories for safe passing. This use case combines V2V for vehicle trajectory, sensor data exchange and fine-grained coordination between vehicles; V2I for intersection monitoring and coordination, speed advisory and signal phase and timing for each and every vehicle; V2N for dynamically updated local map info.
- Use Case 2.2: Traffic jam chauffeur. Scenario type: V2V combined with mMTC and URLLC. The goal is to provide automated driving functionality in traffic jams for increased user comfort and satisfaction. This use case focuses on highly automated vehicles (up to SAE level 4) that would operate on motorways reaching the cross-border junction, in which a driver is not required for vehicular control. The scenario includes UC vehicles operating in roads shared with other testing

vehicles, pedestrians and cyclists or its representation as the dummy targets, all following a designated route towards the border junction. The traffic jam chauffeur application would make automated driving in traffic jams or stop and go conditions more convenient. The application can steer the vehicle and its brakes in an automated way up to a specific speed limit, e.g. up to 70 km/h, monitoring at the same time the speed of the preceding vehicle and its surroundings through several sensor sources (e.g. to detect hidden objects and act accordingly), as well as the trajectories of nearby testing vehicles. The application integrates and makes use both of the lane assist feature of the vehicle to provide an active lane guidance function, as well as the traffic jam chauffeur for automatic braking and acceleration. The application would therefore enable lateral and longitudinal guidance, relieving also the driver from the responsibility for steering.

2) Use Case Category 3: Sensing Driving

- Use Case 3.1: Sensor info sharing for cooperative situation awareness. Scenario type: V2V, V2I combined with mMTC and URLLC. The goal is to allow connected vehicles travelling in close proximity to each other in motorways, to form part of a group to exchange sensor data, collaborate and thus guarantee the safety for all involved nearby vehicles. Description: Connected vehicles can enhance the perception of their environment beyond what their own sensors can detect so as to have a more holistic view of the local situation. In this regard, sensor info sharing enables the exchange of raw or processed data gathered through local sensors or live video data among vehicles, Road Site Units (RSU), UEs of pedestrians and V2X application servers, in order to achieve cooperative situation awareness. For example, in the event of an accident risk, the vehicle itself can independently take preventive actions, such as emergency braking. Currently, vehicle safety is entirely dependent on the functionality of onboard sensors, cameras, and radars, so it is expected that V2V communications will be more effective than such current embedded systems designed by car OEMs. The On Board Unit (OBU) system of the vehicle, would collect such in vehicle sensor information and process them to react for example to any dangerous situations based on specific parameters, such as cruising speed, the distance from a remote obstacle, the presence of a passing vehicle in the blind spot, etc. However, although such onboard technologies are increasingly reliable, there might still be errors in the calculation process. On the contrary, V2V communication protocols will improve the performance in the security field, since, by making all the vehicles close to interact each other, they will help the car in danger (for instance, driver's sleep, a component malfunction, obstacle in the lane, and so on) to undertake a more effective choice to solve the emerging problem.
- Use Case 3.2: Connected maintenance. Scenario type: V2N, combined with eMBB & mMTC. The goal: To create a preventive maintenance framework and a new maintenance business model through which the data collected from the sensors, in combination with predictive analytics, enable long-term maintenance and repair services thus enabling customer support to follow the vehicles owners throughout the lifetime of their vehicles. Description: Connected maintenance is a use case provided by the collection and real time processing of sensor data within vehicles to monitor the health status of certain vehicular elements. Even AR/VR can be used for remote assessing of a maintenance issue from mechanics in order to have enhanced awareness of the issue in conjunction with the usage of the sensors. Sensors are installed in several elements within vehicles to monitor the vehicle's condition. Such IoT-based mMTC type of sensors collect, analyse and forward vehicular data to a centralised system in the network. The data received from these connected cars, can then be analysed further so as to identify whether a vehicle requires any maintenance service. Furthermore, the system can generate emergency alerts to both the drivers and the maintenance teams. In addition, car OEMs could provide automatic software updates to vehicles' electronic control units (ECU), to keep them up to date with new security, safety and new functionality patches.
- Use Case 3.3: Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Collision Avoidance. Scenario type: V2D, V2P, combined with mMTC & URLLC. The goal is to extend safety protection for VRU by enabling reliable interaction between active vehicle and surrounding passive VRUs. Description: In addition to cooperation with

other vehicles, the interaction of vehicles with VRUs (e.g. pedestrians, disabled people on wheelchairs, blind people, pets, bicycles, motorcycles) especially at cross walks and spots without line of sight, can help increase the road safety and reduce the traffic accidents through early notifications about potential collisions and their avoidances with appropriate actuation system manoeuvres. A critical requirement for realising this use case is the real-time accuracy of the positioning information covering pedestrians, cyclists and vehicles. In such a scenario, the driver of a vehicle, intending to make a left turn, even though he/she cannot directly see the pedestrian wishing to cross the road due to obstructed view by another passing vehicle, is alerted to the presence of a VRU via a warning issued by the VRU collision avoidance application. To be able to issue the warning, the application would have calculated the trajectories of vehicles and the VRU, by using the geometry of the intersection, the road and its surroundings and determine the risk of collision. Various methods can be employed to detect the presence of VRUs, for example local sensors, cameras, radars, 802.11p, positioning systems, including the 5G communications network. The involvement of the communications network is meaningful if the VRU has a mobile network enabled smartphone. Other relevant scenarios include the generation of warning notifications by roadside units, other vehicles' C-ITS systems based on sensor data and cooperative actions enabled via cooperative messaging exchange in a bi-directional manner. This use case could benefit from distributed MEC in the context of exploiting local context with positioning information, such as Radio Network information and location APIs, to improve the accuracy of the positioning information of all traffic actors.

3) Use Case Category 4: Uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go

- Use Case 4.1: 360° Immersive multi-user gaming on the go. Scenario type: eMBB with URLL. The goal is to provide uninterrupted 360° immersive multi-user gaming experience to validate how business continuity can be achieved across borders and across different means of transport (i.e. automotive, railways and maritime) Description: Besides classical services, (e.g. web browsing, file download, email, social networks, etc.), a strong increase is expected in UHD multimedia, as it will become immersive and highly interactive to provide ambient media consumption not just at home but also on the move, with content capable of adapting to the user's ambient for viewing. In particular, gaming will expand into a full 360° immersive multi-sensorial environment, which will result in a more realistic experience, improved ability for users to collaborate and without any limitation on the number of simultaneous players. Apart from ultra-fast connections and low latencies, 360° immersive multi-user gaming on the go requires a uniform user experience, i.e., one that does not significantly change due to the mobility or position in the cell or even when crossing EU borders. This use case involves the setting up of a collaborative video game using a distributed approach as well as the testing of various AR/VR applications that will be provided by BRA. The game will consist on a multi-user gymkhana, where different items spread around the world can be tracked and found by the players. These elements will be displayed as AR graphics integrated in the images captured by the device camera (smartphone, tablet or laptop), or as VR graphics if the device in use is a head mounted display. The objective of the game will be to solve different riddles in order to find where the next item, treasure or creature is, in order to map all the virtual surroundings and hidden mysteries around the user's area, in interaction with other online players. For this use case, existing assets from the MobiAR⁵ project will be leveraged and extended. The game session will commence either during the transportation of the passengers from their vehicles towards the borders for

⁵ MobiAR was a Spanish funded project lead by Telefónica I+D, where smart phones cameras where used to provide a touristic immersive experience to users while visiting different monuments in a city. BRA implemented the graphics engine in MobiAR and populated it with different assets, monuments and other attractions in the city of San Sebastian. Based on the geolocation of the device, users could see superimposed, 3D versions of the elements in real time, along with relevant cultural information.

embarkment and continuation of the gaming session to other multi-modal means of transport, such as railways and ferries.

- Use Case 4.2: 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move. Scenario type: eMBB with URLLC. The goal is to provide seamless uninterrupted 3D virtual collaboration experience to validate how business continuity can be achieved across borders and across different means of transport (i.e. automotive, railways and maritime). Description: New 5G capabilities will enable real-time audio-video experience to retransmit high resolution and high dynamic range video. In this use case, a business passenger participates to a 3D real-time virtual conference meeting on-route from one country to another (e.g. Latvia Estonia or Estonia Finland). The business user initiates the application whilst being in his/her automated vehicle and whilst on the move, continues the session until he/she is embarked on an international railway or a ship to transfer him/her to the other country. As interlocutors take part in the meeting, they are integrated in the virtual scenario. Also, they can share interactive objects (e.g. a new part in a car design, a TAC captured knee of a patient, or a pie chart describing the distribution of clients), that all the participants can manipulate concurrently and in real time. The 3D virtual session lasts beyond the entire duration of the journey, so it is important that the service remains uninterrupted and with the same high Quality of Experience throughout the entire journey from one means of transport to another and also when crossing borders. Other cross borders settings will also be validated, i.e. rail to rail, vehicle to ship and rail to ship combining sat 5G connectivity.

4) Use Case Category 5: Multimodal services

- Use Case 5.1: Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics. Scenario type: mMTC combined with hybrid positioning. The goal is to provide seamless tracking of massive amount of goods to validate how business continuity can be achieved across borders, across different means of transport (i.e. automotive, railways and maritime) massive Machine Type of Communications (mMTC) and across terrestrial and satellite 5G operators. Description: Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross border logistics could boost the consumption of data traffic on the move, as massive amounts of IoT-based tracked goods consume massive Machine Type of Communications (mMTC) telecom data. The Gulf of Finland between Estonia and Finland suffers from poor 2G/3G/4G mobile connectivity and therefore, scalable IoT-based tracking is currently not feasible. 5G can enable the realisation of such mMTC service types which can be combined with hybrid accurate positioning through appropriate IoT-based sensors/tag devices that are attached to the cargo. UC5.1 therefore involves setting up of a test cargo on a ship, onto which IoT location sensors are attached so that it can be tracked throughout its journey from the source to the destination. The aim is to validate how effective and continuous visibility of goods tracking can be achieved at any time throughout the entire multimodal journey of goods traversing multiple EU member states over terrestrial (i.e. road and railways) as well as maritime means of transport. In addition, other relevant cross border settings will be validated, e.g. within international railways crossing EU borders commencing from one EU country (e.g. Latvia) to Estonia and continuation of the journey to a ferry (e.g. across the Gulf of Finland from Tallinn to Helsinki).
- Use Case 5.2: 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight. Scenario type: eMBB combined with mMTC and URLLC. The goal is to provide proactive and multimodal management of passengers and freight when crossing borders including across terrestrial and satellite 5G operators. The 1st phase focuses on the cross-border communication and provides mechanisms for notifications on approaching passengers and freight and assignment of necessary resources in the destination network. To achieve this, it is important to leverage heterogeneous inputs from vehicles, transferred goods and people and to propose prediction algorithms for predicting traffic in the destination network and plan accordingly the needed resources. It is also important to include actions for configuring the telecommunication network and the vertical. The multimodality aspect can be tackled in the 2nd phase where unloading of freight from trucks and/or railways and loading them to ships can take place in addition to passengers' movement. This can be

combined with automated checking of freight (towards zero-touch), conducting logistics operations and informing authorities. A notification message could be sent by the vehicles to a road-side unit, or a small cell or a macro cell, and through this notification we can notify the network about the types of traffic and demand levels in order to configure accordingly the destination network through a configuration message. Network slicing will accommodate different types of traffic that can be mapped to eMBB (e.g. capturing images of freight from high quality cameras in the border area), mMTC (e.g. for large amount of sensors/tags which are attached to freight and vehicles) and URLLC (critical IoT-based data to trucks/vehicles in case of emergency or dangerous freight which may pass the border area) service classes.

- Use Case 5.3: FRMCS telemetry operation. Scenario type: mMTC combined with eMBB & URLLC. Its goal is to improve service availability and performance for telemetry operation of railways through FRMCS. UC5.3 focuses on FRMCS bearer flexibility and in particular telemetry operation to allow a certain level of independence between railway applications and the underlying transport system, thus improving service availability and performance. A train is located in a railway depot where only WLAN coverage (non-5G access) is provided as part of the FRMCS, through which the FRMCS users are connected to. A railway operator user initiates a telemetry operation data session towards the diagnostic entity. Once the train leaves the depot and enters the 5G coverage area, the FRMCS equipment adapts the transmission of the telemetry data session to the most QoS effective 5G radio RAN station, thus ensuring uninterrupted and continuous telemetry session whilst the train is on-route. This setting may involve other voice/data applications using other combinations of access systems at specific locations.

6 5G-ROUTES Research Ethics Policy and Protocols

The objective of the ethics tasks in the 5G-ROUTES project is to ensure that the innovation brought about by the project is in line with European ethics and moral values. This is done by applying the theory of Value Sensitive Design, an approach which aims to integrate a wide range of human and moral values into the design of information technology.

In other words, Value Sensitive Design implies that a normative framework is defined, and that the designers of a system – in this case the 5G-ROUTES project – integrate this framework into their work, thus recognising that systems are rarely ethically neutral, and that human well-being, human dignity, justice, welfare, and human rights can be served by integrating them into technological design.

Therefore, as a first step, a usable normative framework must be established for the 5G-ROUTES project, and specific ethics requirement must be derived on the basis of this framework. Thereafter, we can assess to what extent the 5G-ROUTES project already complies, and which requirements warrant particular attention in the future.

6.1 Scope

Article 34.1 of the Grant Agreement provides that “the beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with: (a) ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity) and (b) applicable international, EU and national law. [...] The beneficiaries must ensure that the activities under the action have an exclusive focus on civil applications. [...] In addition, the beneficiaries must respect the fundamental principle of research integrity — as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity [...] and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices and refrain from the research integrity violations described in this Code”.

- As regards research integrity, Deliverable D7.5 entitled “Project Quality Handbook v1.0” contains Section 6 in which procedures of internal control, monitoring and reporting of project results are specified;
- Concerning compliance with applicable international, EU and national law, Article 34.2 of the Grand Agreement adds that “activities raising ethical issues must comply with the ‘ethics requirements’ set out as deliverables in [WP8 of the DoA]”.

Given the information and analysis provided in the previous sections, this chapter outlines the policy embedded in the ethics management guidelines for the 5G-ROUTES consortium on research ethics. This chapter:

- Presents the 5G-ROUTES project ethics management safeguards (Section 6.2);
- Defines recommendations for the recruitment provisions (Section 6.3), which include criteria and procedures for human beings’ involvement in the project research activity, should the case arise;
- Defines recommendations for protecting individuals’ data (Section 6.4), which includes an overview of the EU framework on personal data processing and;
- Defines protocols for protecting project data (Section 6.4).

5G-ROUTES innovation, testbed and field-scale activities will be continuously monitored by the EP of the project, led by its Chair. 5G-ROUTES will strictly follow H2020 national legal ethical requirements of the relevant directives, as presented in the previous Sections, where the research is performed.

Furthermore, 5G-ROUTES will not touch upon any of the following fields of research:

- research activity aiming at human cloning for reproductive purposes;
- research activity intended to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such changes heritable;
- research activities intended to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement, including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer.

The 5G-ROUTES Ethics policy also covers:

- A clear description of the EP, their participants and their roles in Section 5.2.1.2 (part of Ethics advisory, controlling and monitoring).
- The research legal and ethics backgrounds as described in the previous Sections.

The next sections of this Deliverable aim to cover at minimum the ethics requirements in the 5G-ROUTES project. In addition, as aforementioned, health and safety provisions have also been considered.

6.2 5G-ROUTES Ethics and Risk Management Safeguards

6.2.1 Ethics Management Safeguards

To insure compliance with ethics principles, 5G-ROUTES has established several safeguard mechanisms:

- The 5G-ROUTES' Research Ethics Protocol (i.e. this chapter) has been defined for guiding project activities.
- The project Legal & Ethics Leader, as well as the project DPO has been appointed in the person of:
 - Mr. Henri Schasmin (TTU)
- In addition, the following partners have already appointed their own internal DPO who will closely collaborate with the project's DPO:
 - Fatima Aparicio Prieto (ATOS)
 - Miguel Churruca Soto (BRA)
 - Ioannis Chalinidis (CERTH)
 - Nadina Del Moral Roura (CTTC)
 - Christos Skoufis (eBOS)
 - Aija Mezsarga (EDI)
 - David Quesada (ENIDE)
 - Ülle Tiitmaa (EEE)
 - Helen Hindrichson-Nairis (EVR)
 - Ioanna Fergadiotou (ILS)
 - Melani Gurdiel (IQU)
 - Edite Stipra (LMT)
 - Peter Suhren (SWM)
 - Atro Lehtinen (VEDIAFI)
 - Seppo Viinikainen (VTT)
 - Isidoros Monogioudis (WINGS)

As of today, the following partners (ADS, ADSF, PV, TELIA, VED) have not yet appointed their DPO. This list will be updated in the context of the preparation of the D5.7 – Data management Plan.

- As described in 2.5.1.2, the Ethics Panel (EP) has been established. This panel is chaired by the project Legal & Ethics Leader and includes legal advisors of the participating members (with experience and expertise related to ethics, privacy, and legal issues). The EP is available for providing advices and shall monitor the compliance of the project activities with the 5G-ROUTES' Research Ethics Protocol. At the time of writing the current document, the composition of the Ethics Panel is as described in Section 5.2.1.2.
- The following email address shall be used for internal use when seeking appropriate communication related to ethics issues: henri.schasmin@taltech.ee. In addition, a dedicated mailing list will be created once all DPOs have been appointed.
- In case any specific issue should arise for the EP members provide insufficient expertise to deal with, an external expert will be invited to the Ethics Panel and will act as an independent reviewer and consultant.

- The 5G-ROUTES' Project Management Board (PMB) has been established; it is composed of different manager roles that ensure the quality conduct of the research activities, as well as the protection of the rights of participants' rights protection.
- A follow-up document will update the progress made during the project, namely D7.8 "Report on legal and ethics monitoring final version" which will be delivered at month 35 just before the end of project on month 36.
- **Ethics control and monitoring:** The EP will be obliged to comply with the Ethics Policy of the project, the European and national/regional regulations and practices and report back to the Project Management Board about the ethics compliance of the relevant activities as well as any issues that may arise respectively. This will be done by means of the meeting minutes and the live documents as reported in Section 5.2.1.2. In addition, in regard to the use cases, a summary of each pilot site will be obtained and the information will become the **ethics profile** of each pilot site. This will be done by having the investigating partner responsible for conducting trials involving human participants filling in an **Ethics Controlling Report** and its respective EP member making sure that there no missing information and/or ethical issues raised through the Ethics Checking Form. Annex III provides the template for the Ethics Checking Form and Annex IV provides the relevant template for the Ethics Controlling Report. In addition to the 5G-ROUTES Controlling Report, ethics approvals will be obtained from their institution's Ethics Committee (or relevant authoritative body), or from the Academic Ethics Committee of TTU in case. Ethics approvals from local relevant authorities will be sought as needed, if necessary.
- In case that an answer in the **Ethics Checklist Form** is negative without adequate justification, the Chair of the Ethics Panel evaluates its severity and proposes relevant mitigation measures to the Project Management Board or decides to convene the Ethics Panel for looking more in depth into the respective ethics / legal issue.
- In addition, the diagram in Figure 2 presents the procedure of ethical considerations from planning to realisation of a test bed or use case activity.

The EP will supervise and ensure that the ethical guidelines of the project are followed, this is done in close collaboration with WP3 - 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness and WP4 - Large-scale cross-border CAM field trials. The leading partner at each test bed and Use Case site will be responsible for the submission and approval of the pilot research protocol to the local/regional and/or institute Ethics Committee required in each country. The EP of 5G-ROUTES is the one responsible for keeping track of the process through a dedicated checklist (see Annex III – Ethics Checklist Form).

The Consortium shall implement the research project in full respect of the legal and ethical national requirements and code of practice and will achieve that using the Local Ethics Representatives and the Ethics Controlling Reports. Whenever authorisations must be obtained from national bodies, those authorisations shall be considered as documents relevant to 5G-ROUTES. Copies of all relevant authorisations and approvals shall be submitted to the project coordinator prior to commencement of the relevant part of the research project. The Ethics Policy of the project will be continuously monitored and updated if needed. Future updates will take into consideration the Ethics Controlling Reports outcomes.

Finally, it should be highlighted that balanced gender representation should be also attained to the possible extent (see section 4.2).

Figure 2. Procedure of ethical considerations from planning to realisation of a test bed or use case activity

6.2.2 Ethics and Legal Risks Identification and Mitigation Strategy

It is not possible to conceive a procedure, investigation, or process which would be without any risk. One of the most important factors in the assessment of risk is the perception of the prospective participant of the importance of risk. The participant's life situation may substantially influence the way in which a risk is perceived. The end point of the process is the consent given by the person to be part of the research project, having considered all aspects of the process and asked all relevant questions.

All relevant information will be given to the participants. This means that the project 5G-ROUTES will be carefully explained.

Physical risks stemming from traffic safety issues will be minimised thanks to the H&S protocols and are expected to be at the same level as those experienced by the average traveller throughout their daily driving when in a hurry, fatigued, stressed, etc.

Below, a preliminary risk identification and mitigation strategy is presented. As required in the DoA, the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project including the opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 will be provided in D8.2: POPD - Requirement No. 2 on M6.

Table 7. Preliminary ethics and legal risks identification and proposed mitigation strategy

Ethical & Social risks	Description	Ethics Risk Management in 5G-ROUTES
Application of overarching Ethical and legal framework	All relevant legislation, regulation and ethical codes will be considered; they are defined how they are met in terms of processes, timing and responsibilities	5G-ROUTES EP will oversee the ethical concerns involved in the project and the ethics approval processes at project level. Annex III includes the information required to be addressed (Ethics checklist) which partners might be required to obtain prior any testing takes place.

<p>Transparency and consent of the Use Case participants</p>	<p>The informed consent administration ensures that the user accepts participation and is informed about the project and the Use Cases objectives. Written consent is obtained after participants are informed. Information provided is clear and understandable about their roles (tasks and rights), research objectives and methods applied, duration of study and participation (if they differ), confidentiality, safety and risk related issues as well as the benefit for them and the project. These aspects are managed in the next column (on the right) and are depicted in the informed consent form template (annexed in D8.1 and D8.2).</p>	<p>The basic parts of the 5G-ROUTES informed consent will include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The objective of the study, its duration and methodology; 2. Possible risks, discomforts and side-effects (also related to traffic safety); 3. Privacy and data protection procedures; 4. The possibility to decline the offer and to withdraw at any point of the process (and without consequences) 5. Information about the data controllers, processors and data manipulation in general; 6. Identification of data controllers and processors; 7. Contact person.
<p>Privacy and data protection</p>	<p>Only anonymised data will be processed and, therefore, no personal data will be processed in relation to specific user. The name will not be connected to other characteristics (e.g. age, gender, nationality, health and/or mobility profile). Anonymous data handling falls under the European and national legislation for the lawful processing of personal data.</p> <p>To avoid risks related to the processing of personal data such as identity theft, discriminatory profiling or continuous surveillance, the principle of proportionality has to be respected. Data can be used only for the initial purpose for which they were collected.</p> <p>Anonymisation or pseudonymisation is a way to prevent violations of privacy and data protection rules. Processing has to be limited to what is truly necessary and less intrusive means for realising the same end have to be considered.</p>	<p>The project identifies which data protection rules apply and establishes a list of risks and potential solutions; taking due account of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – What kind of data will be processed? – What is the purpose of the processing? – Will the data exceed the purpose of the study? – Are there procedures ensuring that data is processed only for the originally identified purposes? – Who is the owner of the data? – Is data connected to other information? – Will data be commercially exploited? – What is the duration of the storage of the data? – Where will the data be stored and according to which national legislation? – Who will access the data? Are they secured? – Will the user be recorded? – Which metrics will be implemented? – Who will supervise the data protection? <p>These questions will act as a foundation for preparing the private data information consent form (in D8.2). The collected information will consequently feed the</p>

		private impact assessment (PIA) process that will be managed by eBOS within D5.7 (M06) and D5.8 (M33).
Safety & certification of autonomous systems/vehicles	Data collection and evaluation activities should not entail any undue risk for participants other than the ones they will encounter in their everyday travelling and living activities.	Existing technologies adhere to all current and relevant standards in the area (of ETSI TC ITS - Application Requirements and Services, ISO TC 204 - Intelligent transport systems CEN TC 278 - Intelligent transport systems, etc.) as they be collected and listed within A15.5. Further standardisation and certification aspects will be handled in the aforementioned activity. 5G-ROUTES technologies will be verified, validated before actual deployment to large-scale field studies (Use Cases) in test beds performed in WP3, T3.4.

6.3 Recruitment rules

In case external research participants will be involved, their recruitment will be governed by three key principles [15]:

- The participation is voluntary and can withdraw from research activities at any time they wish;
- Recruitment is appropriate to the research question and methods; and
- Participants are chosen in a non-discriminatory manner.

6.3.1 Recruitment Criteria

6.3.1.1 Participants Freedom

In case research activities with humans will be performed, 5G-ROUTES will strictly follow [16], [17], and [18]. For each relevant activity, the procedures and criteria details will be readily made available to the project external participants. It is at the participant's discretion as to whether s/he wishes to participate in the activity or not.

6.3.1.2 Inclusion and Non-Discrimination

In case human beings will be involved in use cases and testbeds/test site activities, 5G-ROUTES will comply with the relevant national and international regulations. Special attention will be paid to the observance of the DIRECTIVE 2006/54/EC [19] of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (recast), Article 14 of and Protocol 12 to the European Convention on Human Rights, as well as the Handbook on European non-discrimination law [20] issued by the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) – 2018 edition.

6.3.1.3 Research Integrity

Research integrity builds upon good research practices. By ensuring a good research environment, increased trust in researchers is achieved, and they will be better engaged with the practical, ethics and intellectual challenges inherent to their research. Therefore, the key principles of research integrity are essential recruitment criteria in 5G-ROUTES: "reliability", "honesty", "respect", "accountability" (European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity [12]).

6.3.1.4 Vulnerable populations

Recruitment of participants that will take place in certain Use Cases (e.g. Use Case 3.3) will likely involve vulnerable road users who will participate depending on the Use Case plans, specifications, requirements and criteria. Vulnerable road users (VRUs) are considered “*by the amount of protection in traffic (e.g. pedestrians, motorcycles and cyclists) or by the amount of task capability (e.g. disabled people on wheelchairs, blind people, the young and the elderly). Vulnerable road users do not usually have a protective 'shell', and also the difference in mass between the colliding opponents is often an important factor. Vulnerable road users can be spared by limiting the driving speed of motorized vehicles and separating unequal road user types as much as possible*” (SWOV Vulnerable Road Users Fact Sheet, 2012).

Vulnerable users (i.e. homeless, drug and alcohol users and abusers, immigrants, etc.) will not be recruited to participate in any Use Case across pilot sites that are conducted by the 5G-ROUTES Consortium. As required in the DoA, D8.1: H - Requirement No. 1 will clarify whether and in which Use Case vulnerable individuals/groups will be involved and the measures to protect them and minimise the risk of their stigmatisation. The research protocol should describe the context of a proposed research population (country or community) that create conditions for possible exploitation or increased vulnerability among potential Use Case participants, as well as the steps that will be taken to overcome these and protect the rights, the dignity, the safety, and the welfare of these participants. D8.1 will be submitted by EEE on M6.

6.3.2 Recruitment Procedures

In case research participants will be involved, the general rule is that the identification and selection thereof will be carried out by the use-case leaders. They will recruit participants from their respective networks, in accordance with the profile determined for the purposes of testing the 5G-ROUTES tools. Research participants will be invited to partake in accordance with their role within the organisation that can be potentially relevant for the 5G-ROUTES project activities. The procedures listed in the next paragraphs will be followed to respond to determined risks and obstacles.

6.3.2.1 Rights of Participants Procedures

Complying with the European Charter for Researchers, 5G-ROUTES has the responsibility for the people involved in the research action and for their rights, safety, well-being and interests (or dignity, integrity, rights, and autonomy), as is also the case for all the communities that are engaged and involved in the research i.e. for the “society at large, in terms of the contributions research can make in effecting socially useful and valued development and change, but also in terms of avoiding potential misuse or unintended consequences of research results.” [17]. Thus, participation in 5G-ROUTES project activities will be fully voluntary; all participants will be given the opportunity to ask questions and receive understandable answers before making decisions about their participation.

Informed consent forms and information sheets: recruited participants will be provided with informed consent forms and information sheets. The consent process will be elaborated and provided in D8.1 (H - Requirement No. 1) as a separate document, accompanied by the various consent templates and information sheets. However, the informed consent process, either for recruitment or for testing, remains an integral part of 5G-ROUTES Ethics Policy. These templates will be re-visited and adapted before any testing takes place. They will be also reviewed by the EP. Each pilot site representative is responsible to ensure the correct translation and adaptation of all relevant consent forms as well as their safekeeping. In Annex V (Information Sheet) and Annex VI (Informed Consent Form) preliminary templates for the cross border trials provided as examples.

Withdrawal: participants will also have the right to withdraw themselves and their personal data, as well as to terminate their participation in the research at any time; they will also be reminded about their rights before participation. This information will be provided to participants by means of an information sheet. The consent form will be signed twice with one signed copy provided to the participant.

Acknowledgement of research results. 5G-ROUTES Pilot participants will be informed that the main results and outcomes of the Pilots will be shared with them and they be in an accessible format (e.g. odt, *.pdf, html, printed, in Braille, ...), if such requirement arises.

Continuous support during testing. The test and/or use case team members during testing will ensure participants feel comfortable and not coerced or tired. Questions are allowed during testing, in designated times. Participants should be informed about this possibility beforehand. The contact person details will be provided to the participant along any information and contacts in case the participants have any questions after the end of the testing session.

Reimbursement: All participants will be strictly volunteers. In case of recruited participants, the appropriate reimbursement mechanisms will be set in place. These mechanisms will be approved by the EP before they can be administered. In the cases where reimbursement incentive is foreseen, claimants (research interviewees) should be made aware of the status of the payment in opt-out letters using the following terminology: *“If you do take part in the face-to-face discussion/trial/survey/testing, you will receive XX € in cash, as a ‘thank-you’ gift for your help with this study. This will not affect your entitlements to benefit in any way”*. In general, it will be avoided to apply reimbursement in the form of incentive payment. The incentivization strategies will be decided and described within the D8.1 Deliverable.

5G-ROUTES policy on privacy, transparency, confidentiality, risk assessment and acknowledgement to the participants of 5G-ROUTES studies: Each test bed and use case responsible should explain the following to recruited participants:

- **General scope of 5G-ROUTES** and short reference to its objectives.
- **Scope and short description of the test / use case** and the respective study.
- **Value of participation.** The supervisor will explain the benefit of the participation to the project, i.e. how it will assist in the research realised in the project and why the participant should consider joining this study as a research participant (benefits for the participant and the public in general).
- **Risk assessment.** The major identified risk is related to invoking unrealistic hopes and expectations for personal benefits in terms of automated and improved mobility. This will be counteracted by explicitly communicated information about the limitations of such personal benefit and harm. The test beds and use case plans will ensure that no harm will be brought upon the participants and pre-testing activities will provide the necessary assurance. None of the use case related tasks (either in test beds or in the field pilots) is anticipated to have any (side-) effects on the physical or mental integrity or health of the participant, other than the ones existing in their everyday travelling/transport activities. As diverse user groups are addressed (including potentially disabled persons, and various stakeholders, such as operators, service providers, etc.), all sites will internally review the Use Case plans and will reach a decision on the inherent risks for all possible addressed user groups. Harm is not anticipated in any way, but the Use Case partner in charge will ensure that they will explain the situation to recruited participants, in particular with respect to the safety and security issues i.e. if there any kinds of harm that could be experienced during the trials and what are the measures that have been taken in order to prevent that and reduce any such chances. Also, when there are safety related issues (i.e. in-vehicle information and scenarios of use) all necessary precautions will be taken. In all cases, the test sites will abide with the internal and/or national safety regulations applying in their sites.

6.3.2.2 No Discrimination Procedures

Avoiding discriminatory outcomes before the research activities (i.e. during the participants' selection) and after it (i.e. during the dissemination and exploitation phases) will be supported by enforcing all the necessary measures to safeguard against stigmatization of groups and individuals on account of their gender, race, religion, sexual orientation, political beliefs, ethnicity, and other social features. 5G-ROUTES will strive to recruit 1) women (targeting a female/male ratio as close as possible to 1:1) and 2) persons of diverse backgrounds via

inclusive, clear, accessible, and transparent procedures. Any exclusionary practices, marginalization, devaluation of research, and stereotyping will be considered unacceptable.

6.3.2.3 *Ensuring Good Understanding of Procedures*

For ensuring that information is properly and effectively understood by the participants, for each project activity involving human beings, the 5G-ROUTES partners shall:

- Provide customised protocols including details on the procedures. Moreover, the chosen criteria to be used will be readily made available to the participants in order to ensure the specificity requested by [21] for the information sheet;
- Ensure that potential participants will be fully informed and will not feel pressured, coerced, threatened or stressed by researchers into giving consent; to do so, different procedures will be deployed to ensure the respect of freedom of the participants, as request by [21];
- Deception. Researchers do not deceive by any means prospective participants about research that is reasonably expected to cause physical pain or severe emotional distress. Researchers explain any deception that is an integral feature of the design and conduct of an experiment to participants as early as feasible, preferably at the conclusion of their participation, but no later than at the conclusion of the data collection, and permit participants to withdraw their data. No deception will take place in 5G-ROUTES Pilots and the user will be informed at all evaluation stages about the objectives and the procedures related to the test beds and use cases and how their data will be handled, processed, and stored. In the case a functionality of a service is simulated, they will be informed but they will be asked to perform and react as if the situation was real.
- Debriefing. Researchers provide a prompt opportunity for participants to obtain appropriate information about the nature, results and conclusions of the research, and they take reasonable steps to correct any misconceptions that participants may have of which the researchers are aware. The debriefing must be documented and will be signed by both sides. Summaries and copies of research reports will be given to research participants in appropriate accessible formats (e.g. larger font size, use of simple text accompanied by photographs, oral communication, etc.) and communicated through dissemination channels (e.g. the website, social media, etc.).
- Provide any information (verbal, written or recorded) in a language and in terms that the participants can fully understand. This ensures the unambiguity (as well as misunderstanding and incomprehension) required by [21];
- Explicitly state that participation is voluntary and that anyone has the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw his/her participation, samples or data at any time, without any consequences. This ensures the respect of freedom of participants to adhere or not;
- Describe the aims, methods and implications of the research, the nature of the participation and any benefits, risks or discomfort that might ensue. This ensures the right of participant to be informed about any consequences (also potential risks);
- State which procedures will be implemented in the event of unexpected or incidental findings (in particular, whether the participants have the right to know or not about any such findings);
- Provide researchers contact details for participants to contact the Project Consortium for information and decide whether they wish to join in.

A template for the informed consent in case of anonymous involvement (i.e. no personal data are collected during the activity) is included in this document as Annex VII: Anonymous Informed Consent Template.

Moreover, a Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template contains the template in case of personal data collection, included as Annex VIII.

The informed consent form is composed of two parts: 1) the Information Sheet and 2) the Consent Form. Both parts shall be distributed among participants prior the activity starts. The informed consent form, duly signed by

the individual or his/her legal representative, shall be kept secure and on file for the whole duration of the project by the activity organizer, who shall notify it to the Ethics Panel using the respective email address.

The specificity of each activity requires producing an ad-hoc customised information sheet and consent form. Therefore, the abovementioned templates shall be customised accordingly to the specific activity.

6.3.2.4 Health and safety (H&S) for human participants

Section 4.4.2 provides the relevant provisions for H&S considerations.

6.3.2.5 Good Research Practices

In 5G-ROUTES, the respect of the principles of the research integrity will be guaranteed by adopting specific research practices so as to:

- Enhance the research environment;
- Stimulate training, supervision and mentoring;
- Promote open, transparent and non-discriminatory research procedures;
- Incentivise collaborative working;
- Give results of publication and dissemination avoiding research misconducts such as: whistle blowing, fabrication, falsification and image manipulation; plagiarism; duplicate and redundant publication.

6.4 Privacy, Personal Data Processing and Protection

6.4.1 EU Framework on Personal Data Processing and Protection Overview

The current EU framework on data protection, the General Data Protection Regulation [21] defines (article 4, n.(1)) the personal data as any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or will more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.

Given the above, the scope of personal data is broad, including anything that can uniquely identify an individual, such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that individual. In addition, article 4 of the GDPR includes definitions of specific personal data, which are mostly related to sensitive and peculiar aspects of the personality of physical subjects, including:

- Genetic data: personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person and which result, in particular, from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question [article 4, n. (13)];
- Biometric data: personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopy data [article 4, n. (14)];
- Data concerning health: personal data related to the physical or mental health of a natural person, including the provision of health care services, which reveal information about his or her health status [article 4, n. (15)].

Further, processing of personal data being able to reveal racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation are, in general, prohibited and may be processed exclusively in some specific cases.

These categories of personal data that are subject to additional protections, as they are considered as the hardcore of the protection that must be ensured to individuals by privacy regulations.

In the eventuality of personal data processing, the GDPR includes a range of requirements, constraints and controls to govern how personal data should be collected, stored, processed, retained, and shared. The most significant are listed in what follows:

- 1) Individuals shall provide explicit consent to data collection – “consent by default” is no valid. The organization seeking consent shall also provide clear information on how that data will be used, for how long it will be retained, and how it will be shared with third parties. Individuals can retract consent at any time, without prejudice. Additional permissions shall be requested from the individual if the data is to be used for processing purposes beyond the original consent.
- 2) A Data Protection Officer (DPO) shall be designated in cases identified by art. 35.
- 3) Organisations shall conduct an internal assessment to understand personal data risk exposures. GDPR Art. 35 defines what are the cases when a DPIA is mandatory and all partners should monitor if a formal DPIA is required by the nature of research activities. If needed partners can consult the project DPO and the EP for guidance.
- 4) If the processing would result in a high risk in the absence of measures taken by the organisation to mitigate the risk, the supervisory authority prior to processing shall be consulted.
- 5) Data protection shall be by design and by default, requiring data protection mechanisms to be embedded into products and services from the earliest stage of development, and the adoption of strictest privacy settings without any manual input from the end user.
- 6) Individuals rights shall be guaranteed:
 - a. Individuals shall have easier access to their data, enabling them to review what data is stored about them and how it is processed, who it is shared with, along with the ability to migrate that data between service providers without restriction.
 - b. Individuals shall have the "right to be forgotten", also known as “right to erasure”, so that there is no legitimate reason for an organization to refuse the request of individuals to definitely remove their personal data when they ask for it to no longer be retained.
- 7) Profiling and automated decision making shall ensure the profiling data subjects’ rights.
- 8) Any data breach shall be notified to the Data Protection Authority.
- 9) Personal data processed for any purpose or purposes shall not be kept for longer than is necessary for that purpose or those purposes.
- 10) **Personal data protection:** No personal data will be centrally stored, without anonymization or pseudonymisation as needed. In case of pseudonymisation, only the persons designated in the DMP will have access to the relation between participant’s code and identity, in order to administer the tests. More on Data Management policy in detail will be discussed in the Data Privacy policy (Section 6.4) and in D5.7 ‘Data Management Plan v1.0’ and D5.8 ‘Data Management Plan final version’.

All those requirements are included in 5G-ROUTES Research Ethics Protocol and illustrated in the following sub-sections.

6.4.2 5G-ROUTES Privacy, Personal Data Processing and Protection Rules

As a general rule, only anonymised or aggregated data (completely disjoined from people identification and profiles) shall be processed related to the participation in the project research process and data generated or processed by the project (e.g. during the pilots). Whenever, for specific reasons, personal data might need to be processed, the interested 5G-ROUTES partner shall remain responsible for the data collected during its own research and will be required to follow the European and national rules on privacy and data protection as well as the ethics rules listed in what follows.

6.4.2.1 *Consent Procedures and Forms*

Explicit consents to personal data collection have to be provided by each potential participant, prior to their involvement in the project activities. The GDPR [21] defines consent of the data subject as any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her. Moreover, the Recital 32 "Conditions for Consent" in [21] states that consent shall be given by a clear affirmative act establishing a freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her, such as by a written statement, including by electronic means, or an oral statement. Consent is not just a simple form or document to be filled and signed by the individual; it is first and foremost a process that involves the individual and the entity entitled to collect and manage data.

The most important aspect in the informed consent process is to unambiguously ensure that individual is properly informed in a comprehensive language and that individual effectively understands the research activity, how data are used and the risks to be harmed (if any). In this perspective, the process of informing project activities participants and ensuring their understanding shall be carried out by considering the following conditions in order to:

- Ensure the specificity of consent, an ad-hoc tailored consent form shall be distributed to all individuals, prior their involvement in project activities that collect personal data. In case of processing of "special category of personal data", those participating will have a separate consent form, with a paragraph adding more details on the purpose of the processing, the duration of the processing, the plans for storing and sharing that data and their rights of access, correction and erasure. This data will be destroyed as soon as possible after the specific objectives to which the data relates are achieved;
- Reduce the risk of ambiguity, misunderstanding and incomprehension, the consent form to be filled and signed shall be translated into participant's mother tongue;
- Reduce the risk of access to the information, the consent form shall be provided to participants either in hard copy or online;
- Be compliant with the "Privacy by Default" principle, as well as to respect the freedom of individuals, consent form shall not provide "default checked answers" that can dissuade to express particular opinions and trigger to "pure acceptance" behaviour of participants;
- Respect the freedom of the individuals, informing phase and understanding phase shall be carried out by ensuring necessary time to take the right decision and consequently sign or not the consent form.

For complying with specificity requirements, a consent form shall be produced and customised for each activity. Thus, a template to be customised for the specific project activity is included in this document as Annex VIII: NonAnonymous Informed Consent Template.

The informed consent form is composed of two parts: 1) the Information Sheet and the 2) the Consent Form. Both of them shall be distributed among participants prior the activity will start. The informed consent form, duly signed by the individual or his/her legal representative, shall be kept secure and on file for the whole duration of the project by the activity organizer, who shall notify it to the Ethics Panel using the relative email address. Informed Consent is needed to be obtained both for personal data and audio/video records management. In this respect, there should also be acknowledgement on video/sound recording sessions and screen capturing facilities (if applicable). If this is applicable, written consent is obtained before the session starts with a dedicated type of consent form (annexed in D8.1). If the participant does not agree to this, the recording will not take place.

6.4.2.2 *Designation of the Partner DPO*

In the eventuality of personal data processing by a consortium partner, this partner shall notify the project Ethics Panel. Moreover, in compliance with H2020 Ethics rules, the partner involved in collecting and/or processing

personal data shall nominate a DPO well before the collection/processing will take place and communicate it to the project Ethics Panel and the Project Management Board. Under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ex Art. 37(1), a DPO must be designated in any case where:

- 1) The processing is carried out by a public authority or body, except for courts acting in their judicial capacity;
- 2) The core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing operations which, by virtue of their nature, their scope and/or their purposes, require regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale; or
- 3) The core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9 and personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10.

Art. 37(5) of the Regulation details what are the requirements and skills for the role:

The DPO, who can be a staff member or contractor, shall be designated on the basis of professional qualities and, in particular, expert knowledge of data protection law and practices and the ability to fulfil the tasks referred to in Article 39.

In particular, the tasks expected by Art. 39 of the GDPR include:

- 1) Informing and advising the controller or the processor and their employees who carry out processing of their data protection obligations (Art. 39(a)).
- 2) Monitoring compliance with the EU and national data protection rules, including the assignment of responsibilities and awareness-raising and training of staff involved (Art. 39(b)).
- 3) Providing advice where requested as regards the data protection impact assessments (DPIAs) and monitoring compliance and performance (Art. 39(c)).
- 4) Cooperating with the supervisory authority (Art. 39(d)).
- 5) Acting as a contact point for the supervisory authority on issues relating to processing (Art. 39(e))

6.4.2.3 Data Management Plan (DMP)

While the initial version of Data Management Plan (D5.7) will be delivered in month 6, we deem necessary to highlight that during the project, it is important to consider carefully and document the ways of collecting and processing data. Specifically, it is important to specify:

- 1. who is responsible for data;**
- 2. who has access to project data;**
- 3. what will happen to the data after the closure of the project.**

The Data Management Plan will describe the procedures that will be followed throughout the project.

Below, we list the principles that will be incorporated in the procedures set in the 5G-Routes Data Management Plan:

1. Data acquiring, including:

- 1.1 Self-collecting;
- 1.2 Re-using previously collected data;
- 1.3 Public (Open) Data collecting;
- 1.4 Re-using data collected by others;

1.5 Buying data.

2. Data description, including:

2.1 Data types;

2.2 Data integration;

2.3 Data preservation;

2.4 Data permissions.

3. Data formats, including:

3.1 Data formats choice explaining;

3.2. Using open formats;

3.3 Using standard formats;

3.4 Using Machine-readable formats;

3.5 Recommended data formats.

4. Data volume, including estimating the data volume at the end of the project: preservation, access, backup, data exchange, hardware and software, technical support, expenses.

5. Data creation and collection methods and procedures, including:

5.1 Naming the existing standard procedures and methods;

5.2 Available data standards;

5.3 Ensuring data quality (availability, integrity, confidentiality);

5.4 Errors handling (input errors, problematic values).

6. Software.

7. Organisation of Data:

7.1 Systematisation;

7.2 Folder and file organisation;

7.3 Cloud-based code repository;

7.4 Metadata.

Taking into account article 35 of the GDPR, each partner shall evaluate if the personal data processing is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the type of processing. In this case, the partner shall conduct a data protection impact assessment

well before the collection/processing will take place and report its results to the project Ethics Panel to be included in deliverable D7.8 “Report on legal and ethics monitoring final version”.

The GDPR Article 35 states that a DPIA is necessary where an organisation, processes personal data in way that is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of an individual. GDPR Article 35(3) states that DPIAs are mandatory in a number of processing scenarios where an organization performs automated decision-making based on personal data profiling, large scale processing of special categories of data or systematic monitoring of publicly accessible areas on a large scale.

In particular, a DPIA is required where an organisation:

- Uses systematic and extensive profiling with significant effects; or
- Processes special category or criminal offence data on a large scale; or
- Systematically monitors publicly accessible places on a large scale.

6.4.2.4 Declaration on Compliance and/or Authorisation

In case of collecting and/or processing personal data, the partner shall check if a declaration on compliance and/or authorisation is required under national law for collecting and processing personal data. If yes, copies of the declaration on compliance and/or authorisation shall be kept on file for the whole duration of the project, by the partner. If no, declaration on compliance or authorisation shall be required under the applicable national law, a statement from the designated Data Protection Officer that all personal data collection and processing will be carried out according to EU and national legislation shall be kept on file for the whole duration of the project, by the partner.

In both cases, the above documentation shall be submitted to the project Ethics Panel to be included in deliverable D7.8 “Report on legal and ethics monitoring final version”.

Both actions shall be carried out well before the collection/processing will take place.

6.4.2.5 Data Protection by Default and by Design

Partners are requested to adhere to what defined in Art. 5 of the GDPR, so that personal data shall be:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject (‘lawfulness, fairness and transparency’);
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes (‘purpose limitation’);
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed (‘data minimisation’);
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay (‘accuracy’);
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed; personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this Regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject (‘storage limitation’);
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures (‘integrity and confidentiality’);

- the controller shall be responsible for, and be able to, demonstrate compliance with ‘accountability’.

6.4.2.6 *Individuals Rights*

The GDPR is designed to provide EU citizens with more control over their own personal data. Therefore, appropriate procedures and state-of-the-art technologies shall be applied for data collection, storage, protection, retention, destruction, and confirmation. Details on those procedures are defined in the project Data management Plan (DMP, i.e. D5.7 Data Management Plan v1.0 and D5.8 Data Management Plan final version).

6.4.2.7 *Automated Individual Decision-making, Including Profiling*

As stated by Art. 22 of the GDPR, the data subject shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal impacts concerning that person or correspondingly altogether affects the person in question. Automated processing and profiling are authorised if the decision is:

- Necessary for entering into, or performance of, a contract between the data subject and a data controller;
- Authorised by Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject, and which also lays down suitable measures to safeguard the data subject’s rights and freedoms and legitimate interests; or
- Based on the data subject’s explicit consent.

In case of automated processing and profiling, the data controller shall implement suitable measures to safeguard the data subject’s rights and freedoms and legitimate interests, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.

Decisions referred by art. 22(2) shall not be based on special categories of “special category of personal data” (art. 9(1)), unless the data subject has given explicit consent (art. 9(2)(a)) or it is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest (art. 9(2)(g)) and suitable measures to safeguard the data subject’s rights and freedoms and legitimate interests are in place.

6.4.2.8 *Data Encryption and procedures.*

Security of Personal Data. According to General Data Protection Regulation Article 32 - the project team shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risks, including **the encryption of personal data**. Appropriate software solutions suitable for all project participants are used to encrypt the data. This appropriate technical solution for data encryption will be decided by the project members, taking into account the recommendations of information security experts.

6.4.2.9 *Data Breach and procedures.*

In case of data breach, the GDPR states that disclosure within 72 hours must be made to the local Data Protection Authority, enabling individuals to be informed and take appropriate remedial action, while in case of organisations’ non-compliance with the GDPR provisions, substantial financial recourse will be made against them.

Procedures and requirements are following:

1. The project participant shall immediately notify the data breach to the Data Protection Officer of his/her institution and project.
2. The Data Protection Officer shall notify the data breach to the data protection supervisory authority within 72 hours.
3. The Data Protection Officer shall immediately take appropriate measures to remedy the data breach and to establish the circumstances of the incident.

4. The Data Protection Officer shall, if necessary, contact the data subjects whose personal data are affected by the data breach.
5. The contact details of the Data Protection Officers and the Data Protection Supervisory Authorities are set out in the Annex to this document.

6.4.2.10 Data Retention Time and procedures.

Personal data generated or managed by the project shall be destroyed as soon as possible after the specific objectives to which the data relates are achieved.

Data will be retained for as long as necessary and in no case longer than 3 years after project completion. If a project member considers that certain data need to be retained for more than 3 years after the end of the project, he/she shall coordinate this with the Data Protection Officer. The data shall be stored in a secure environment. The appropriate environment to data storage be decided by the project members in consultation with the Data Protection Officer.

6.4.2.11 Data Deletion and procedures.

The data shall be deleted as soon as possible after the need to use the data has ceased. The data will be deleted securely by overwriting the data using special software. The deletion of the data and the appropriate software will be decided by the project members in consultation with the Data Protection Officer.

6.5 Project Data, including Research Information and Business/ Trade Secret Confidentiality

Given the potentially confidential nature of data to be exchanged, data should only be made available on a strict need-to-know basis, and it should be appropriately secured against access or use by unauthorised parties.

The CA has already defined in its Section 10 the rules for the non-disclosure of Confidential Information in the project, so that all information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Party (the “Disclosing Party”) to any other Party (the “Recipient”) in connection with the Action during its implementation and which has been explicitly marked as “confidential” or “secret” at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated in writing within 30 calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as Confidential Information by the Disclosing Party is “Confidential Information”.

Moreover, there might be some specific cases where confidential information generated or managed by the project (e.g. data related to non-public deliverables) might need to be disclosed to specific persons/entities for specific purposes. This is the case for instance of the External Advisory Board members that will convey valuable feedback about the project activities. Those cases shall be approved by the whole project consortium and a non-disclosure agreement will be requested to ensure that the external people/entity doesn’t use the information without the project approval. The non-disclosure agreement prepared for the EAB members is enclosed in the current document as Annex IX: Non-Disclosure Agreement for the External Advisory Board.

7 Conclusions and Next Actions

This deliverable has described the work performed in WP7, Task 7.4 “Legal framework, ethics & gender balance”. This includes the identification of the main references (i.e. international ethics standards, international and national legislations and codes regarding the legal and ethics concerns) that lay the foundation for the 5G-ROUTES legal and ethics background framework.

The Background framework is constantly evolving and requires to be continuously monitored for ensuring the compliance of project activities with respect to current EU legal framework and research ethics concerns.

Based on the description of the use cases (still under development during the editing of this document), this deliverable foresees the potential legal and ethics concerns. Further analysis of the 5G-ROUTES project process and methods envisioned additional legal and ethics concerns (i.e. personal data protection and confidentiality of project information), and specifically these relate to EAB involvement in the project (i.e. participation to meetings and revision of deliverables), as well as participants in testbeds/test site (in case of end-users external to the project consortium will be involved).

By adopting a “concerns and safeguards” approach to foresee and address ethics issues, the document proceeded in the definition of the code of conduct, the 5G-ROUTES Research Ethics Protocol, to be respected during the whole project lifecycle, including the definition of Ethics Panel and its role, individuals recruitment rules, safeguards for ensuring privacy and personal data protection (i.e. information sheets and consent procedures), as well as for ensuring project data confidentiality (i.e. non-disclosure agreements).

In case of needs, the Research Ethics Protocol will be accordingly revised and enhanced with the objective of ensuring the observance and promotion of good research practices and the principles that underpin them.

The second version of this document (D7.8) will be delivered at month 35 (just before the end of project) and will report on the monitoring activity and the refinement (if needed) of the Research Ethics Protocol.

Finally, this deliverable provided the 5G-ROUTES consortium with templates for information sheet, consent form and non-disclosure agreement for External Advisory Board.

8 References

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Annex I – Human participation related activities

Table 8 provides a detailed description of human participation in the 5G-ROUTES project activities.

Table 8. Human participation related activities per WP

Activity	Description	When to be addressed	Target audience	Relevant deliverable (month) & Task Leader partner
WP1 – Requirements analysis, use cases and preparation for CAM trials (M1-M24)				
T1.1 - Definition and detailed analysis of CAM use cases, scenarios, specifications for technological enablers and target KPIs (technological & business)	The aim of this task is to capture the requirements from the end-user CAM stakeholders, including the articulation of detailed use case scenarios and usability needs, and relevant target technological and business KPIs, which will be validated in the field trials. A requirements capture will involve the documentation of CAM end-users needs and opinions about new innovative vertical use cases that require 5G performance capabilities in the domains of automotive, railways, transport & logistics, IoT and infotainment.	M1-M23	End-User CAM stakeholders. End-user analysis.	<p>D1.1 (M4): Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0.</p> <p>D1.2 (M23): Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0.</p> <p>T1.1 Leader: ADSF.</p>
T1.4 – Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results	This deliverable will describe the methodology for the assessment, and addresses processes for interaction with research participants, but the task itself will not interact with persons outside the consortium.	M1 -M24	Consortium partners and End-User CAM stakeholders, including customers of the CAM consortium partners. End-user acceptance.	<p>D1.7 (M3): Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0.</p> <p>D1.8 (M24): Testing framework for the technological and business validation</p>

				and benchmarking of the results v2.0 T1.4 Leader: VTT.
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WP2 – Development of technological enablers for CAM trials (M1-M27)

T2.2 – AI-based End-to-End (E2E) slicing optimisation and innovative spectrum usage for CAM services	Dry-run interworking tests will be performed to verify proper operation of network from spectrum allocation and usage prior to live deployment in large-scale field trials.	M1 -M25	Potential tracking of human experimenters via their smartphone, to enable precise resource allocation. This would take place during the final testing of the developed algorithms and would only involve volunteers from the participating partners. A clear and understandable consent form is provided to the human experimenters informing them about the data to be logged. Data logging follows GDPR guidelines and is anonymized to protect the privacy of the human experimenters.	D2.3 (M8): Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0. D2.4 (M25): Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0. T2.2 Leader: WINGS.
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WP3 – 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness (M4-M28)

T3.4 – Lab trials and operational	Lab-trials (test-beds) will be conducted to assess the	M9-M28.	Mainly only personnel of the	D3.8 (M13): Report on lab trials findings
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<p>readiness for large scale field trials.</p>	<p>performance of the network and the CAM ecosystem and technically validate the proper operation of the use cases in lab environments, including the connectivity of the on-board units, network infrastructure, the behaviour of autonomous vehicles, so as to reduce the ambiguities prior to large-scale field trial validation. Lab trials will be conducted over three 5G testbeds, i.e. CTTC in Barcelona, TTU in Tallinn and VTT in Tampere.</p>		<p>consortium partners (project team members) planned. Depends on the use case, and should be verified with the use case leaders.</p>	<p>and field trials operational readiness v1.0.</p> <p>D3.9 (M19): Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness v2.0.</p> <p>D3.10 (M28): Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness v3.0.</p> <p>T3.4 Leader: VTT.</p>
<p>WP4 – Large-scale cross-border CAM field trials (M10-M34)</p>				
<p>T4.2 – Large-scale cross-border field trials execution.</p>	<p>Field-trials (use-cases): large-scale CAM field trials will be conducted in Valga city across the borders of Latvia and Estonia. These will be validated in the Tallinn port as well as in ship liners across the Gulf of Finland from Tallinn port to Helsinki port.</p> <p>These will involve automated test vehicles, end-user devices and CAM applications.</p> <p>The execution of all use cases will be performed over 3 iterative cycles, each spanning over a period of 6 months to ensure appropriate testing and validation of the relevant KPIs.</p>	<p>M14-M34.</p>	<p>Consortium partners and possibly external participants</p>	<p>D4.3 (M20): 5G CAM field trials v1.0.</p> <p>D4.4 (M27): 5G CAM field trials v2.0.</p> <p>D4.5 (M34): 5G CAM field trials v3.0.</p> <p>T4.2 Leader: EEE.</p>
<p>T4.3 – Performance evaluation and lessons learned.</p>	<p>Questionnaires: the performance of each use case will be evaluated from the KPI perspective and test users will provide feedback,</p>	<p>M14-M34.</p>	<p>Human participants in field trials. Consortium partners and</p>	<p>D4.6 (M20): Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned v1.0.</p>

	requirements and suggestions for further improvements in a series of feedback loops connected to WPs 1-3.		possibly external participants.	<p>D4.7 (M27): Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned v2.0.</p> <p>D4.8 (M34): Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned v3.0.</p> <p>T4.3 Leader: IQU.</p>
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WP5 – Commercialisation, innovation management and standardisation (M1-M34)

<p>T5.4 Standardisation contribution and spectrum allocation recommendations.</p>	<p>– The task foresees regular conference calls with targeted standardization community.</p> <p>In addition: the task foresees promoting the project at standardisation-related workshops, panels, and summits.</p>	M1-M33.	Human participants (non-consortium members) in interviews / conference calls.	<p>D5.9 (M5): Report on standardisation activities and spectrum allocation recommendations v1.0.</p> <p>D5.10 (M33): Report on standardisation activities and spectrum allocation recommendations v2.0.</p> <p>T5.4 Leader: ADSF.</p>
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WP6 – Dissemination, Communication and scale-up (M1-M36)

<p>T6.1 Dissemination and communication activities.</p>	<p>A range of activities is planned. The target audiences will be identified, ranging from general public through scientific and academic communities up to specific 5G stakeholders and market actors. The dissemination and communication channels and actions as defined in Section 2.2.1 (DoA, Annex 1, part B) will serve as a baseline. Below, the ones</p>	<p>M1-M36.</p> <p>The approximate timing of the listed activities is specified where known.</p> <p>i. TBD ii. TBD iii. M27 iv. M25</p>	<p>Human participants (i.e. stakeholders; end-users from non-consortium members; see detailed list of target audience groups in Table 2.4a of the DoA – Annex 1 part B) in dissemination events.</p> <p>i. TBD ii. TBD</p>	<p>D6.1 (M5): Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v1.0</p> <p>D6.2 (M20): Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v2.0.</p> <p>D6.3 (M36): Dissemination & Communication</p>
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	<p>organized by the Consortium partners are listed.</p> <p>i. Joint dissemination actions and events (CTTC)</p> <p>ii. Tutorials under the framework of important IEEE conferences & PhD schools (TTU)</p> <p>Workshops (WS):</p> <p>iii. Focused group WS</p> <p>iv. 1st Scientific Workshop</p> <p>v. 2nd Scientific Workshop</p>	v. M33	<p>iii. customers of the vertical sectors i.e. automotive, railways, shipping, transport & logistics, infotainment /other</p> <p>iv. academic and industrial communities</p> <p>v. academic and industrial communities</p>	<p>plans and activities v3.0.</p> <p>T5.4 Leader: CTTC.</p> <p>The respective activities are led by the following partners:</p> <p>i. CTTC</p> <p>ii. TTU and CTTC</p> <p>iii. ATOS; ILS</p> <p>iv. CERTH; VED</p> <p>v. IQU; CTTC</p>
T6.2 – Engagement of external SMEs.	Participation in competition and in the 5G-ROUTES in major 5G events of persons from SMEs and spin-off of research institutes.	M1-M32.	Human participants from SMEs and spin-off of research institutes	<p>D6.5 (M16): Information package for external SMEs to facilitate the design of new CAM applications v1.0.</p> <p>D4.7 (M32): Information package for external SMEs to facilitate the design of new CAM applications v2.0. .</p> <p>T6.2 Leader: WINGS.</p>
T6.3 – 5G-PPP collaboration activities, recommendations and scale up.	Collaboration activities with non-consortium members / stakeholders: participation in 5G-PPP working groups with entities from other 5F-related projects that are relevant to the project through monthly telcos for	M1-M36.	Human participants from Universities, RTOs, Industry, Public/Private associations	<p>D6.7 (M35): Report on joint planning activities with 5G-PPP.</p> <p>D6.8 (M23): Report on technical, business, security, privacy, policies and regulatory</p>

	the effective dissemination of project results and cross-fertilisation of ideas and concepts.			recommendations v1.0. D6.9 (M31): Report on technical, business, security, privacy, policies and regulatory recommendations final version. T6.3 Leader: ATOS.
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Annex II – Health and safety regulations in 5G-ROUTES

5G-ROUTES confirms that, during its evaluation and demonstration activities, will conform with all the appropriate Health and Safety (H&S) procedures on departmental/institutional/regional/national level both for entities' staff as well as with regard to external participants. The overview of the respective regulations for the 5G-ROUTES test sites is provided in the following Table 9.

Table 9. Health and Safety (H&S) regulations in 5G-ROUTES

5G-ROUTES site	Test	Partner	H&S Local/national /institutional guidelines /regulation/standard [Name/Title]	H&S protocol description (brief)	Application level (Departmental/ Institutional/ Regional/ National)	Documentation (link/document)	Relevant to staff/external users/both
5G-Test (Barcelona)	bed	CTTC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC
5G-Test (Tallinn)	bed	TTU	TalTech Occupational Health and Safety Management Regulations	The directive is issued based on clause 9) of § 11 of TalTech Statutes.	Institutional	https://upload.ttu.ee/show/file/4UQS54:6ac1676c133547e0d6b5293065c2d2c4.pdf	Both
5G-Test-bed (Tampere)		VTT	Occupational Safety and Health Act, Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, No 738/2002	"The objectives of this Act are to improve the working environment and working conditions in order to ensure and maintain the working capacity of employees as well as to prevent	National	https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2002/en20020738.pdf	Both

			<p>occupational accidents and diseases and eliminate other hazards from work and the working</p> <p>environment to the physical and mental health, hereinafter referred to as health, of</p> <p>employees"</p>			
UC 1.1	EDI	Labour protection law	The legal framework of the occupational safety and health protection system is set up by the Labour Protection Law. The Labour Protection Law transposes the requirements and principles of EU Framework Directive on safety and health at work. The Labour Protection Law and wherewith all OSH system is based on the “principle of prevention of damage” (establishment of safe and harmless work environment, risk assessment and prevention, adaptation of the workplace to the individual needs, etc.).	National	https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/26020-labour-protection-law	Both
UC 1.2	EDI	Labour protection law	The legal framework of the occupational safety and health protection system is set up by the Labour Protection Law. The Labour Protection Law transposes the requirements and principles of EU Framework Directive on safety and health at work. The Labour Protection Law and wherewith all OSH system is based on the “principle of prevention of damage” (establishment of safe and	National	https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/26020-labour-protection-law	Both

			harmless work environment, risk assessment and prevention, adaptation of the workplace to the individual needs, etc.).			
UC 1.3	VTT	Occupational Safety and Health Act, Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, No 738/2002	<p>"The objectives of this Act are to improve the working environment and working conditions in order to ensure and maintain the working capacity of employees as well as to prevent occupational accidents and diseases and eliminate other hazards from work and the working environment to the physical and mental health, hereinafter referred to as health, of employees"</p>	National	https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2002/en20020738.pdf	Both
UC 2.1	SWM	<p>Italy_Legge 81/08_Testo Unico Sulla Salute e Sicurezza sul lavoro</p> <p>Swarco Mizar internal H&S regulations are also based in the policy mentioned previously.</p>	The provisions contained in the legislative decree consider health and safety standards for workers and workers in the workplace, consolidated in a single regulatory text. The Legislative Decree pursues the aims of this paragraph in accordance with the relevant Community legislation and international conventions and in accordance with Article 117 of the Constitution and the Statutes of the Regions with Special Statutes and the Autonomous Provinces of Trento and Bolzano, and the relevant implementing rules, ensuring	Regulatory policy principles implemented at all levels in terms of health and safety for workers in the workplace	http://lavoro.gov.it/temi-e-priorita/salute-e-sicurezza/Pagine/default.aspx https://www.lavoro.gov.it/documenti-e-norme/studi-e-statistiche/Documents/Testo%20Unico%20Sulla%20Salute%20e%20Sicurezza%20sul%20Lavoro/Testo-Unico-81-08-	Both

			uniformity of the protection of workers and workers on national territory by respecting the essential levels of social and civil rights benefits, including gender, age and status immigrant workers and workers. - Based on "LEGISLATIVE DECREE 9 April 2008, no. 81 Implementation of Article 1 of Law no. 123, concerning the protection of health and safety in the workplace."		Edizione-Giugno%202016.pdf	
UC 2.2	EDI	Labour protection law	The legal framework of the occupational safety and health protection system is set up by the Labour Protection Law. The Labour Protection Law transposes the requirements and principles of EU Framework Directive on safety and health at work. The Labour Protection Law and wherewith all OSH system is based on the "principle of prevention of damage" (establishment of safe and harmless work environment, risk assessment and prevention, adaptation of the workplace to the individual needs, etc.).	National	https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/26020-labour-protection-law	Both
UC 3.1	VTT	Occupational Safety and Health Act, Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, No 738/2002	"The objectives of this Act are to improve the working environment and working conditions in order to ensure and maintain the working capacity of employees as well as to prevent	National	https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2002/en20020738.pdf	Both

			occupational accidents and diseases and eliminate other hazards from work and the working environment to the physical and mental health, hereinafter referred to as health, of employees"			
UC 3.2	TTU	H&S Estonian act: Occupational Health and Safety Act	Estonian Occupational Health and Safety Act adopted by the Estonian Parliament – the Riigikogu – based on which several relevant Regulations of the Government of the Republic and the Minister of Social Affairs have been developed and enacted (the Act came into force on 26 July 1999).	National	https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/511112013007/consolidate https://www.ti.ee/en/work-environment-and-work-relations/legal-acts-regulating-health-and-safety-work	Both
UC 3.3	VED	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC
UC 4.1	BRA	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC
UC 4.2	BRA	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC
UC 5.1	VEDIA	Occupational Safety and Health Act, Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, No 738/2002	"The objectives of this Act are to improve the working environment and working conditions in order to ensure and maintain the working capacity of employees as well as to prevent	National	https://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/kaannokset/2002/en20020738.pdf	Both

			<p>occupational accidents and diseases and eliminate other hazards from work and the working</p> <p>environment to the physical and mental health, hereinafter referred to as health, of</p> <p>employees"</p>			
UC 5.2	WINGS	Occupational Safety and Health Act, Greek Ministry of Labour and Social Security	All issues concerning occupational safety and health (OSH) at national level are under the responsibility of the Ministry of Labour and Social Security. The General Directorate of Working Conditions and Health, responsible for the OSH legislation, strategy, organization, information, education, training and research issues and the Labour Inspectorate (S.E.P.E.), which is the inspection and the enforcement authority for the implementation of the labour legislation, are the principal competent state authorities.	National	http://www.ypakp.gr/	Both
UC 5.3	EVR	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC

Annex III – Ethics Checklist Form

This form must be filled out by the respective Ethics Panel member of the partner leading the testing/ use case.

Ethics Checklist Form	Please circle as necessary	
A) <u>General Information</u>		
1. Ethics Panel (EP) member responsible for this project: [Name, email address]		
2. Partners involved in the testing (also indicate leading partner):		
3. Title of the testing/use case:		
4. Purpose of this research study (briefly explain):		
B) <u>Participants and Informed consent</u>		
5. Have human participants and their involvement been clearly described in the Ethics Controlling Report? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
6. Are recruitment criteria, information sheets and informed consent procedures for this research study/testing in accordance with the Ethics policy/protocols described herein, available and accessible in the appropriate locations? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
7. Does the principal investigator demonstrate good awareness of the informed consent procedures and related documents? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
8. In case the testing includes participation incentives in forms other than the expected benefit from the research outcomes, are these in accordance with the ethics principles as described in D7.7?	Yes	No
9. Will participants receive adequate feedback at the completion of the study, including a debriefing if that is necessary?	Yes	No
10. Have gender balance considerations been taken into account by the principal investigator?	Yes	No
C) <u>Ethics control instruments</u>		
11. Is there a need for ethical approval by a relevant body?	Yes	No
a. If yes, has it been approved?	Yes	No
i. If yes, has it been uploaded to the collaboration platform in folder WP7/T7.4?	Yes	No
12. Does the principal investigator shows good awareness of ethics controls and procedures/documents? (if no, please explain; also inform and instruct accordingly the principal investigator; inform the Ethics Panel by writing when this procedure is completed and the principal investigator shows appropriate awareness)	Yes	No
D) <u>Privacy</u>		

13. Are all the privacy protection related documents (DMP; DPIA-if necessary; information sheets and informed consent forms and Data Processing Agreements) available, appropriate with the responsible persons (DPO, Data Processors and Data Controllers) designated for each relevant participating partner? (if no, please explain; also inform and instruct accordingly the principal investigator; inform the Ethics Panel by writing when this procedure is completed and all documents are available and accessible).	Yes	No
14. Does the principal investigator shows good awareness of procedures/guidelines/legislation for protecting privacy? (if no, please explain; also inform and instruct accordingly the principal investigator; inform the Ethics Panel by writing when this procedure is completed and the principal investigator shows appropriate awareness)	Yes	No
15. Is all of the following information (questions 16-20) clearly documented, available and accessible to the Ethics Panel Members and appropriate for the testing/use case to be performed?	Yes (All)	No
16. Appropriate actions for the investigators do to make sure that the information collected on persons will not get in wrong hands?	Yes	No
17. Appropriate actions that a person can do if he/she wants to find out more about the study, or to complain about the way he/she was treated?	Yes	No
18. Appropriate agreements to ensure that personal information may be shared with any other partner of third party (if applicable)? (If no, please explain)	Yes	No
19. Information in relation to what will happen to any information (including photos, video or voice recordings) given by a person, what are the person's rights, how and how long will it be stored? (If no, please explain)	Yes	No
20. Is 5G-ROUTES Data Protection Policy regarded?	Yes	No
D) <u>Health and Safety (H&S)</u>		
21. In case the research poses risks of physical or psychological harm to participants by using deception, obtaining sensitive information or exposing them for risks in terms of safety and/or security/confidentiality hazards, are appropriate and adequate safety measures and procedures taken and considered by the principal investigator? (If no, please explain)	Yes	No
22. Is the principal investigator aware of the H&S procedures of the testing/research? (if no, please explain; also inform and instruct accordingly the principal investigator; inform the Ethics Panel by writing when this procedure is completed and the principal investigator shows appropriate awareness)	Yes	No
D) <u>Risk Management</u>		
23. In case risks exist, does the research adequately manage these risks by including appropriate relevant risk assessments, procedures, and mitigation measures? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
24. Is there health insurance coverage for persons participating in the testing/ experiments? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
25. Have I as part of the project informed the Ethics Panel in writing about the ethical issues I have identified and of which I am aware?	Yes	No

Annex IV – Ethics Controlling Report

This questionnaire on ethical and legal issues will be filled in by the investigator responsible for conducting trials involving human participants (i.e. **consortium partner leading the testing activity**). The aim is to remind the researcher to consider all relevant ethical aspects before planning and conducting the activity and/or any data collection activities within 5G-ROUTES. The questionnaire is divided into six subsections: General Information, Participants and Informed consent, Ethics control instruments, Privacy, Safety and Risk Management.

Questionnaire on Ethical and Legal issues

A) General information

1. Name and affiliation (i.e. partner) of the person filling out the report:
2. Brief summary of the activity/testing (including type of involvement of human participants):

Have I obtained approval from my institution's ethics committee and /or other relevant responsible body/authority for the planned testing activities involving human participants?

Yes No

If **yes**, please state by whom:

If **no**, please explain why:

B) Participants and informed consent

3. Are you aware of the informed consent procedures that relate to your testing?

Yes No

If **yes**, briefly provide the link to the relevant documents:

4. Do you intend to conduct testing/pilots with individuals who might not understand the informed consent form?

Yes No

If **yes**, briefly explain the procedures you follow in order to obtain informed consent:

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

5. Is there any doubt about the individual's cognitive capacity to consent?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please clarify who will provide consent in such instance: _____

If **no** please continue with the next question.

6. a) Is the informed consent provided in common language to be understood by a lay person?

Yes No

If **no**, why not? Please provide an example of any *termini technici* used within the description.

b) Will the participant be given sufficient time to reflect his/her decision of giving or withholding consent?

Yes No

If **no**, why not? Please indicate the time given to the participant.

7. Is the participant unable to consent for any reason not specifically listed in questions 2 to 4?

Yes No

If **yes**, **no experiment will be performed since these participants are excluded from 5G-ROUTES trials.**

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

8. Is the participant for any reason unable to read the form by him-/herself?

Yes No

If **yes**, please continue with b)

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

b) There are a range of people who are unable to read the consent form; these include those who may also have severe visual impairments (e.g. cataract, glaucoma).

9. Have gender balance considerations been taken into account as per the provisions of D7.7 - Legal framework, ethics & gender balance?

Yes No

In **either case**, please briefly explain how and provide relevant information for male/female research participants (how many, type of involvement):

10. Does your experiment include vulnerable participants?

a) in terms of exposure-related vulnerability (e.g. pedestrians, bicyclists, motorcyclists) ?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (number, type of involvement):

b) in terms of non-exposure related disability (e.g. elderly persons, persons with disabilities or other cognitive impairments / learning difficulties)?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (number, type of disability, type of involvement):

11. Are any illiterate foreseen participants?

Yes No

If **no**, please continue with the question 10.

If **yes**, be advised that an illiterate participant has to provide oral consent which has to be witnessed at least by one person. If that is the case, please name the prospective witness:

Additionally, please answer the following question.

12. Will the oral consent of an illiterate participant that is witnessed be in accordance with your national legislation?

Yes No

13. Is there an international or national legislation, which you must follow *in relation to the type of testing you will be within the 5G-ROUTES project involving:*

a) human participants in general?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

b) participants with cognitive impairments / learning difficulties or other disabilities?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

c) illiterate participants?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

14. Are there participation incentives other than the expected benefits from the research outcomes that are provided to participants?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details.

15. Will participants receive adequate feedback at the completion of the study, including a debriefing if that is necessary?

Yes No

In **either case**, please briefly provide details.

C) Ethics control instruments

16. At which level of your organization / enterprise, *ethics controls* are audited?

- laboratory or workgroup
- division or department
- institution
- local/regional
- national

17. Is there an ethics controlling body in your region / country from which you must obtain ethics opinion/permission, other than those that are responsible within the 5G-ROUTES consortium?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details about the body relevant for you and the procedure that has to be adhered to in order to obtain ethical approval of experiments:

18. Is there an established ethics control procedure which you must follow before performing tests with:

a) human participants in general?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

b) human participants with cognitive impairments / learning difficulties or other disabilities?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

c) illiterate participants?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

D) Privacy

19. Is personal/private information recorded?

- Yes No

20. Is there an established Data Protection Authority issuing procedures / standards you must follow before performing tests with human participants and their personal / private data?

- Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain briefly what corrective actions you will take to ensure privacy of personal data of participants:

21. Do you follow written procedures for protecting privacy?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and state any corrective actions you will take:

22. Do you follow or are you aware of any official national or international guidelines on protecting privacy?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline and provide references:

23. Will you clarify to the participants that all data collected in the activities they are participating in will be kept entirely confidential and that their anonymity will be protected in full?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline and provide references:

24. Do you identify persons and their professions who are authorised to have access to the data collected and / or who have access to any data storage devices, both, paper-based and electronically?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please briefly list these persons and their professions.

F) Health and Safety (H&S)

25. Will your participants follow any specific H&S procedures /protocols /mitigation measures for the purpose of the testing?

Yes No

In **either case**, please provide a brief outline or explanation and provide some references:

26. [Only in case vulnerable participants participate in the testing] Will vulnerable participants be provided with additional H&S procedures/protocols/mitigation measures than those offered to non-disability participants?

Yes No

In **either case**, please explain what and / or why:

27. Will you inform the participants about the H&S procedures / protocols / measures that they need to follow/take?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and the corrective actions you will take:

G) Risk Management

28. Do you have procedures to perform risk-assessment concerning the breach of privacy and / or breach of safety?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and refer to any corrective actions you will take:

29. Is your organisation insured against risks as a result of breach of privacy and/or health and safety risks?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it and state the insurer, if possible:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and state who would cover any insurance-related costs:

30. For conducting research and manage the risk, do you need to involve other organisations (unit, division, department, etc.) which are outside of your direct supervision, the activities of which may influence the ethics/legal integrity of your research and constitute potential threats for the ethical and legal conduct of the activity you are leading?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it and describe the measures you plan to take for avoiding or mitigating these risks:

31. Where any risk assessments relevant to the Framework Directive 89/391/EEC (Health and Safety at Work) and its supporting Directives as per the precautionary principle necessary for the testing?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of these, include the location of relevant risk assessments (e.g. supporting document; link) and briefly describe the identified risks and relevant treatment measures you plan to take for these risks:

Annex V: Information sheet example template

5G-ROUTES Draft Information sheet and informed consent form

Information Sheet

[Date]

5G-ROUTES: 5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

Introduction: [Briefly state who you are and explain that you are inviting them to participate in the research you are doing. Inform them that they may talk to anyone they feel comfortable talking with about the research and that they can take time to reflect on whether they want to participate or not. Assure the participant that if they do not understand some of the words or concepts, that you will take time to explain them as you go along and that they can ask questions now or later.

Example: I am X, working for the Y Research Institute. We are doing research on connected and automated mobility, which is becoming the new trend in transportation, as part the European Union-funded⁶ 5G-ROUTES research project coordinated by ERICSSON EESTI AS (EEE), Estonia in partnership with [Insert NAME of your INSTITUTION⁷]. I am going to give you information and invite you to be part of this research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research. In case there are some words that you do not understand, please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain. If you have questions later, you can ask me about or the staff.]

Purpose of research: [Explain in lay terms why we are doing research within the framework of 5G-ROUTES project. Use local and simplified terms. The language used should clarify rather than confuse. There are guides on the internet to help you find substitutes for words which are overly scientific or are professional jargon.

Example: the purpose of this project is to conduct advanced field trials of the most representative and innovative Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) applications functioning across a designated 5G cross-border corridor ('Via Baltica-North') spanning across 3 European Union member states borders (Latvia-Estonia-Finland) in order to validate the latest 5G features and 3GPP specifications [provide explanations in lay terms for 5G and 3GPP] under realistic conditions, so as to accelerate the widespread deployment of 5G-based interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways, railways and shipways throughout Europe. The findings of this questionnaire / survey / interview / workshop / trial / group discussion / other (Specify:.....)⁸ will assist the consortium partners to capture and assess and/or validate the effectiveness of the 5G-ROUTES 5G CAM ecosystem through relevant use cases.].

Participant selection: [most applicable for vulnerable populations: State why this participant has been chosen for this research. People often wonder why they have been chosen to participate and may be fearful, confused or concerned.

Example: We are inviting people with mobility disability to participate in the research on testing new automated technologies for understanding how our proposed developments may best contribute in alleviating such impairments.]

Voluntary Participation and right to refuse or withdraw: [Indicate clearly that they can choose to participate or not. Participants with cognitive impairment, if any, will be reminded about their participation being voluntary before moving to the consent form and signing it.

Example: Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. You are free to leave at any time, change your mind later and stop participating at any time even if you agreed earlier, without any impacts on you or your future participation in the project.. You are also free to refuse to answer any questions or provide any information that you do not wish to discuss. You have the right to ask questions and receive understandable answers before making any decision].

Information on the 5G-ROUTES applications and systems to be tested: [provide as much give information about the applications as is appropriate and understandable about the system and applications and explain what it does/means (including illustrations of the applications or real demos, depending on availability; participants with cognitive impairments, if any, will

⁶ Grant agreement number 951867

⁷ 5G-ROUTES partner conducting the research and innovation activity will amend all highlighted parts

⁸ Strike through options that do not apply.

receive information with illustrations (i.e. pictures, examples of functionalities, in simple language with no jargon.). Explain the known experience with these applications/services (mainly for technological implementations already in the market).

Example: The system and applications we are testing in this research are called A,B, X. Many of them have been tested before but now they will be integrated and tested in large field scale conditions as one system. The application (s) ABX is made by C, D, E. We know of no problem or risks related to its/their use. Some participants in the research will not be given this/these application(s) we are testing. Instead, they will be given another/other application(s) XYZ. There is no risk, other than usual traffic risk associated with the use of this/these application(s) and no known problems.]

Procedures and Protocols: [Describe or explain the exact procedures that will be followed on a step-by-step basis, the tests that will be done, data that will be gathered. Participants should know what to expect and what is expected of them. Use active, rather than conditional, language. Write "we will ask you to...." instead of "we would like to ask you to...." An illustration of the system and applications, if available, will help participants understand the process better ".]

Duration: [Include a statement about the time commitments of the research for the participant including both the duration of the research and follow-up, if relevant.

Example: The research takes place over ____ (number of) days in total. During that time, it will be necessary for you to come to the testing facility _____(number of) days , for ____ (number of) hours each day. We would like to meet with you for a final validation of the results X months after your last testing.]

Risks: [Explain and describe any possible or anticipated risks. Describe the level of care that will be available in the event that harm does occur, who will provide it, and who will pay for it (e.g. traffic-related risks). A risk can be thought of as being the likelihood that harm may occur. Provide enough information about any risks and relevant mitigation/safety measures that the participant can make an informed decision.

Example: By participating in this research it is there will be no more possibility to be at greater risk than you would otherwise be by driving in usual traffic conditions. While the possibility of this happening is very low, you should still be aware of the possibility. We will try to decrease the chances of this event occurring, but if something unexpected happens, we will provide you with_____.]

Benefits (if reimbursement is used; benefits might not be provided): [Mention only those activities that will be actual benefits and not those to which they are entitled regardless of participation. Benefits may be divided into benefits to the individual, benefits to the community in which the individual resides, and benefits to society as a whole as a result of finding an answer to the research question.

Example: Your participation in this research, is likely to help us find the answer to the research question [state] and the research community / society may benefit from the advancements in automated and connected mobility your participation may result to.].

Reimbursements: [State clearly what you will provide the participants with as a result of their participation. There is no encouragement for using incentives. However, it is recommended that reimbursements for expenses incurred as a result of participation in the research be provided. These may include, for example, travel costs and money for wages lost due to time commitment for testing. The amount should be determined within the host country context.

Example: We will give you [amount of money] to pay for your travel to the place of study taken place/follow-ups/parking and we will give you [amount] for lost work time. You will not be given any other money or gifts to take part in this research.]

Confidentiality: [Explain how the research team will maintain the confidentiality of data.

Example: We will not be sharing the identity of those participating in the research and the record of your involvement in the research will be kept confidential and no-one but the researchers will be able to see it. Any personal data you provide will be handled according to the legal requirements outlined in the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. You have been informed that everything you say will be anonymized. The event data will be recorded via [paper notes/electronic notes/voice recorder/camera recorder] and you can request a copy of these records to review if you wish. I understand that I am also allowed to delete or make any changes to these records if I feel the information I provided could be improved or clarified. I understand that information about my personal involvement in the research will be kept in a secure location at ERICSSON EESTI AS and that my information will be made anonymous when shared with 5G-ROUTES project team. I understand that the data I provide will be [anonymized, pseudoanonymized] and the record of my participation will be kept in a file separate from the project data. Any information about you will have a number on it instead of your name. Only the principal investigator will know what your number is and we will lock that information up with a lock and key. It will not be shared with or given to anyone except [name who will have access to the information]. I understand that the data will be kept for 3 year after the 5G-ROUTES project ends, but my personal data will be destroyed when the project ends.

Sharing of the results: [Where it is relevant, your plan for sharing the information with the participants should be provided. If you have a plan and a timeline for the sharing of information, include the details. You should also inform the participant that the research findings will be shared more broadly, for example, through publications and conferences.

Example: Confidential information will not be shared. There will be small meetings with consortium and these will be announced. After these meetings, we will publish the results in order that other interested people may learn from our research.]

Who to Contact: [Provide the name and contact information of someone who is involved, informed and accessible (a local person who can actually be contacted and of the Coordinator). State how the research has been approved.

Example: This research conforms to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. This procedure has been reviewed and approved by [name of the local IRB and/or the Academic Ethics Committee of TTU], which is a committee whose task it is to make sure that research is conducted in an ethical and legal manner. If you have any questions you may ask them now or later, even after the study has started. In case you are looking for additional information/clarifications for the testing/research that has been conducted, feel free to contact ERICSSON EESTI AS (Project Coordinator: provide [name, address/telephone number/e-mail]) about any queries relating to my data or the project itself.]

Annex VI: Informed consent form example template

5G-ROUTES: 5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

Lead partners: *[Insert name of person/institution conducting the research activity]*

Participant Identification Number for this project:

Please ✓ box

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated <i>[insert date]</i> explaining the above research project and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my participation is purely voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. In addition, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline and can contact Project Coordinator ERICSSON EESTI AS via telephone at +372 6 500 900.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my responses and personal data will be kept strictly confidential.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I give permission for members of the project team to have access to my anonymised data. I understand that my name will not be linked with the research materials, and I will not be identified or identifiable in the report or reports that result from the research.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to take part in the above research project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I received a copy of both the information sheet and the informed consent form.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

(or legal representative)

Name of person taking consent

Date

Signature

(if different from lead researcher) To be signed and dated in the presence of the participant

Lead researcher

Date

Signature

To be signed and dated in the presence of the participant

Copies:

Once this has been signed by all parties the participant should receive a copy of the signed and dated participant consent form, the letter/pre-written script/information sheet and any other written information provided to the participants. A copy of the signed and dated consent form should be placed in the project's main record (e.g. a site file), which must be kept in a secure location.

Annex VII: Anonymous Informed Consent Template

5G-ROUTES: 5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

Information Sheet

5G-ROUTES project is [***Add short project description...***]

You are invited to join the 5G-ROUTES research project to take part of the 5G-ROUTES field study. Please take whatever time you need to read and understand the following text. The decision to join, or not to join, is up to you. If you agree with the content, sign the consent form hereafter.

The aim of this activity is to [ADD HERE THE DESCRIPTION].

Your participation is voluntary and free-of-charge and it will take you [ADD HERE THE TIMEFRAME] minutes/hours. If you accept to participate, you will be asked to [ADD HERE DETAILS]. No risks are foreseen for your participation to this activity. [IN CASE OF FORESEEN RISKS, ADD HERE DETAILS].

The project may stop the field study or take you out of the field study at any time they judge it is in your best interest. They may also remove you from the field study for various other reasons. They can do this without your consent. On the other hand, you are free to stop participating at any time without any obligation.

5G-ROUTES will collect information for the purposes of the 5G-ROUTES project. Only information that is necessary to address the central purpose of the research will be recorded, and the data will be anonymised at the point of collection. Such information will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with the provisions of the “Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU” (2007/C 303/01), “Convention 108 +” of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals and “General Data Protection Regulation” (EU Regulation 2016/679).

The information will be processed for statistical purposes in an aggregated form. The statistical data and the aggregated information may be disseminated in journals, papers, conferences or events. In any case, your name or any information that could identify you or relate to your identity will not be linked with the research materials. If you have any questions about the field study or the project itself, any problems, unexpected physical or psychological discomforts, any injuries, or think that something unusual or unexpected is happening, you are free to contact Mr./Ms. [ADD HERE THE CONTACT PERSON] at [ADD HERE THE CONTACT DATA – EMAIL – PHONE NUMBER].

After reading the Information sheet and voluntarily deciding to take part of the project activity, participants shall sign the following Informed Consent Form. Since the form contains personal data, it has to be kept secure by the activity organiser.

5G-ROUTES Informed Consent Form

	Description	YES	NO
1	I [ADD HERE THE PERSON NAME and SURNAME] agree to voluntarily participate to the 5G-ROUTES field study.		
2	I have read the Information Sheet, and understand what the field study involves.		
3	I understand that if I decide at any time that I no longer wish to take part in this field study, I can notify the researchers involved and withdraw immediately, without any obligation.		
4	I understand that confidentiality and anonymity will be maintained regarding my personal information and it will not be possible to identify me at any research stage in the project.		
5	I have had the opportunity to have all my questions answered to my satisfaction. I've been informed of the data governance given by the 5G-ROUTES project.		

A copy of the information sheet and this signed consent form will be given to the signee.

Signature of Subject or Representative and date: _____

Annex VIII: Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template

5G-ROUTES: 5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

Information Sheet

5G-ROUTES project is [**Add short project description...**]

You are invited to join the 5G-ROUTES research project to take part of the 5G-ROUTES field study. Please take whatever time you need to read and understand the following text. The decision to join, or not to join, is up to you. If you agree with the content, sign the consent form hereafter.

The aim of this activity is to [ADD HERE THE DESCRIPTION].

Your participation is voluntary and free-of-charge and it will take you [ADD HERE THE TIMEFRAME] minutes/hours. If you accept to participate, you will be asked to [ADD HERE DETAILS]. No risks are foreseen for your participation to this activity. [IN CASE OF FORESEEN RISKS, ADD HERE DETAILS].

The project may stop the field study or take you out of the field study at any time they judge it is in your best interest. They may also remove you from the field study for various other reasons. They can do this without your consent. On the other hand, you are free to stop participating at any time without any obligation.

5G-ROUTES will collect information for the purposes of the 5G-ROUTES project. Only information that is necessary to address the central purpose of the research will be recorded, and the data will be anonymised at the point of collection. Such information will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with the provisions of the “Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU” (2007/C 303/01), “Convention 108 +” of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals and “General Data Protection Regulation” (EU Regulation 2016/679).

The information will be processed for statistical purposes in an aggregated form. The statistical data and the aggregated information may be disseminated in journals, papers, conferences or events. In any case, your name or any information that could identify you or relate to your identity will not be linked with the research materials. If you have any questions about the field study or the project itself, any problems, unexpected physical or psychological discomforts, any injuries, or think that something unusual or unexpected is happening, you are free to contact Mr./Ms. [ADD HERE THE CONTACT PERSON] at [ADD HERE THE CONTACT DATA – EMAIL – PHONE NUMBER].

5G-ROUTES will collect information for the purposes of the 5G-ROUTES project. Only information that is necessary to address the central purpose of the research will be recorded. Your personal data will not be transferred outside the 5G-ROUTES Consortium and, in any case, they will not be transferred outside Europe. Your personal data will be securely stored and retained for as long as necessary and in no case longer than 3 years after project completion, and safely deleted afterwards. All collected information will be handled in accordance with the provisions of the “Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU” (2007/C 303/01), “Convention 108 +” of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals and “General Data Protection Regulation” (EU Regulation 2016/679). More details about 5G-ROUTES privacy policy can be found at the following link [ADD HERE THE LINK TO THE 5G-ROUTES WEBSITE PAGE]. If you have any questions about the field study or the project itself, any problems, unexpected physical or psychological discomforts, any injuries, or think that something unusual or unexpected is happening, you are free to contact Mr./Ms. [ADD HERE THE CONTACT PERSON] at [ADD HERE THE CONTACT DATA – EMAIL – PHONE NUMBER].

After reading the Information sheet and voluntarily deciding to take part of the project activity, participants shall sign the following Informed Consent Form. Since the form contains personal data, it has to be kept secure by the activity organiser.

5G-ROUTES Informed Consent Form

	Description	YES	NO
1	I [ADD HERE THE PERSON NAME and SURNAME] agree to voluntarily participate to the 5G-ROUTES field study.		
2	I have read the Information Sheet, and understand what the field study involves.		
3	I understand that if I decide at any time that I no longer wish to take part in this field study, I can notify the researchers involved and withdraw immediately, without any obligation.		
4	I have had the opportunity to have all my questions answered to my satisfaction. I've been informed of the data governance given by the 5G-ROUTES project.		
5	I voluntarily consent with the processing of my personal data in accordance with the provisions of the "Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU" (2007/C 303/01), "Convention 108 +" of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals and "General Data Protection Regulation" (EU Regulation 2016/679).		

A copy of the information sheet and this signed consent form will be given to the signee.

Signature of Subject or Representative and date: _____

Annex IX: NDA template for EAB

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

Non-Disclosure Agreement for External Advisory Board Members

This Non-Disclosure Agreement (“NDA”), is made as of **dd/mm/yyyy** hereinafter referred to as “Effective date”, and is entered into by and between the following parties (each a “Party and collectively the “Parties”):

- (1) Project Coordinator details.

- (2) External Advisory Board member details.

-AND-

The parties in (2)-[] above are hereinafter each referred to individually as an “External Advisory Board Party” and collectively as the “External Advisory Board Parties”.

WHEREAS, the Project Coordinator of project “5G ROUTES” (5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials) funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 951867 has entered into a consortium agreement (the “Consortium Agreement”), with effective date September 2020. The parties to the Consortium Agreement are [] (a “Consortium Party” or together the “Consortium Parties”).

The External Advisory Board Parties are members of an advisory committee (the “External Advisory Board”), connected to 5G ROUTES, but are not necessarily partners in 5G ROUTES (in which case not parties to the Consortium Agreement). The External Advisory Board Parties, will not commit any financial resources to this project but will contribute expertise as identified in the stages of the project, subject to availability and a voluntary approach and without remuneration.

WHEREAS, the Project Coordinator as part of the External Advisory Board meetings, for the benefit of all parties including the Consortium Parties, anticipate the need to disclose information regarding 5G ROUTES (hereinafter referred to as the Project”) to the External Advisory Board Parties which the disclosing Party considers to be proprietary.

The Parties are aware that the Consortium Parties’ undertakings towards each other regarding confidentiality and non-disclosure are governed by the Consortium Agreement and consequently not by this NDA.

NOW, THEREFORE, in consideration of the covenants and agreements herein contained, the sufficiency and adequacy of which are acknowledged, the Parties agree as follows:

1. “Information” as used in this Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) is any information disclosed by a Consortium Party (“Disclosing Party”) to an External Advisory Board Party (“Receiving Party”) related to the Project. Undertakings in this agreement by a Receiving Party is made vis-à-vis the Project Coordinator and the relevant Consortium party.

2. All information in a tangible form (including information transmitted electronically) which the Disclosing Party desires the Receiving Party to treat as “Confidential Information”, shall be marked by the Disclosing Party with the legend “CONFIDENTIAL” or “PROPRIETARY” in order to identify its confidential nature. If Confidential Information is disclosed orally, visually or in any other non-tangible manner of disclosure, such information shall also be entitled to protection as Confidential Information, if the information disclosed is identified as Confidential Information at the time of disclosure and is subsequently reduced to appropriate written form and furnished to the Receiving Party within one (1) month of the time of original disclosure.
3. Each Receiving Party hereto agrees to receive Information for the sole purpose of improving and evaluating the progress and research results of 5G ROUTES.
4. For the term of the confidentiality obligation provided for in this NDA, the Receiving Party agrees to hold the Confidential Information received from the Disclosing Party in confidence and not to disclose such Confidential Information to any other Party or party and to use such Confidential Information only for specified purposes in this NDA. The Receiving Party agrees that it will use the same degree of precaution and safeguards as it uses to protect its own information of like importance, but in no case with any less than reasonable care. For the avoidance of doubt, the Receiving Party also agrees that it will not use Confidential Information to develop or produce any product or to develop or perform any service without an agreement in writing with the Disclosing Party authorizing such development, production or performance.
5. The obligation of confidentiality shall not apply to:
 - (i) Information, which is now or later becomes publicly available through no act or failure to act on the part of the Receiving Party in violation of this NDA; or
 - (ii) Information, which the Receiving Party can prove is rightfully acquired by the Receiving Party from a third party which is not under any obligation of confidentiality with respect to the Information; or
 - (iii) Information, which the Receiving Party can prove is developed by or for the Receiving Party independently of information which the Receiving Party is required to keep confidential under this NDA; or
 - (iv) Information, which is required to be disclosed by national law or any court having jurisdiction over the Receiving Party; or
 - (v) Information, which the Receiving Party can show it possessed before the Disclosing Party disclosed it to the Receiving Party
6. The Receiving Party may disclose Confidential Information to its employees who need to know and use Confidential Information in furtherance of the purposes of this NDA and who are under an obligation to keep the Confidential Information confidential to the same extent as the Receiving Party.
7. The Receiving Party will return Confidential Information to the Disclosing Party upon written request by the Disclosing Party. However, the Receiving Party will be allowed to retain one (1) archival copy of any document if required by national law.
8. The Agreement shall cover Confidential Information disclosed by the Disclosing Party to the Receiving Party for the purpose of this NDA. Termination of obligations of confidentiality and non- use shall not be construed, however, as a grant of any license under patent rights or copyrights of the Disclosing Party, any other Party or party.
9. Nothing contained in this NDA shall obligate any Party to enter into any agreement with any other Party for the purpose of any development project or for any other purpose. Also, this NDA does not include, expressly or by implication, any representations or warranties as to the accuracy, efficacy, completeness, capabilities, safety or any other qualities whatsoever of any Information or materials provided under this NDA, nor does this NDA grant the Receiving Party any license on the Information of the Disclosing Party.

10. This NDA shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Estonia. All disputes arising out of or in connection with this NDA, which cannot be solved amicably, shall be finally settled under the Rules of Arbitration of the International Chamber of Commerce by one or more arbitrators appointed in accordance with said Rules. The place of arbitration shall be Brussels, if not otherwise agreed by the conflicting Parties. The arbitration will be final and binding upon the Parties.

Nothing in this NDA shall limit the Disclosing Parties' right to seek injunctive relief or to enforce an arbitration award in any applicable competent court of law.

11. This NDA can be amended or modified only by an amendment in writing signed by all Parties. Parties foresee to enlarge the number of External Advisory Board Parties and agree to amend this NDA for accession upon request.

12. This NDA constitutes the entire agreement and sole understanding of the Parties with respect to the subject matter hereof, save for the Consortium Parties' undertakings towards each other regarding confidentiality and non-disclosure which are, as stated above, governed by the Consortium Agreement and not by this NDA.

13. An entity becomes a Party to this NDA upon signature of this NDA. This NDA shall have effect from the Effective Date and will expire upon complete fulfilment of 5G ROUTES. The secrecy obligations last until five (5) years after the expiration of this NDA. Provisions and/or obligations which naturally are intended to continue to exist after the expiration of this NDA, survive such expiration.

14. The Information is provided 'as is' without any kind of warranty, express, implied and/or statutory, including but not limited to the fact that the application and/or use of the Information does not infringe the intellectual property rights and/or other rights of a third party. The Parties are liable towards each other only for damages, which are the direct result of a culpable shortcoming namely a breach of contract, on the part of the breaching Party under this NDA. The Parties are not liable to each other for any kind of other damages, losses, expenses, indirect and/or consequential damages, which the Receiving Party suffers, arising out of and/or in connection with the accuracy, completeness and/or other quality issue with respect to, and/or the application and/or use by the Receiving Party of the Information.

15. The Receiving Party acknowledges and agrees that all property, including intellectual property, in the Information shall remain and be vested in the Disclosing Party.

16. By signing this NDA, the Receiving Party consents to ERICSSON EESTI AS (as the project coordinator) keeping their personal data (name, email and affiliation) for the purposes of the 5G ROUTES External Advisory board and only. All parties reserve the right to be removed (opt-out) from the project repository, at any point via direct contact to the project coordinator, in full compliance with the EU GRPR policy.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Parties have accepted the terms and conditions of this NDA and caused it to be duly signed by the undersigned authorized representatives in separate signature pages.

Company name: ERICSSON EESTI AS

Signature(s):

Name(s):

Title(s): 5G ROUTES Coordinator

Date:

Company name:

Signature(s):

Name(s):

Title(s):

Date: